

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

Technical Report for period
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Authors: Juraj Franců, Vladimír Kolejka,
Petr Jirman, Patrik Fiferna, Eva Hudečková,
Miroslav Pereszlényi, Róbert Prochác, Aleš Havlín (CGS),
Vladimír Opletal, Milan Pagáč, Jiří Gavor, Štěpán Káňa (MND),
Anders Nermoen, Eric P. Ford, Roman Berenblyum,
Anton Shchipanov, Alexey Khruenko (NORCE),
Martin Klempa, Michal Matloch Porzer, Martin Kašing (VSB),
Petr Kolář, Zuzana Jechumtálová, Petr Jedlička (GFU)

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1 INTRODUCTION

CO₂-SPICER project was officially launched on 1 November 2020 and its implementation has been planned for 3.5 years. It is being carried out by a consortium of 5 organisations from the Czech Republic and Norway under the leadership of Czech Geological Survey. For the purposes of this report, Project Partners’ acronyms were used (Tab. 1-1).

Tab. 1-1: Acronyms of Project Partners used in the report.

Project Partner	Acronym
Czech Geological Survey	CGS
MND a.s.	MND
NORCE Norwegian Research Centre AS	NORCE
VSB – Technical University of Ostrava	VSB
Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences	GFU

The project is divided into 10 Work Packages (Fig. 1-1). Each Work Package has its clearly defined leader, objectives, description of work and results. Work packages are structured into Tasks, each with a defined Task leader.

Fig. 1-1: Project structure of CO₂-SPICER.

The work in the 3rd project period was fully oriented to the achievement of the main project objective – preparation of a pilot CO₂ storage project at the Zar-3 field in SE Czech Republic. Significant progress in this direction has been made in all Work Packages.

The work was governed by the detailed work plan described in the document “Project content & Detailed description of Work Packages” (attachment 5 to project application). Chapter 2 of this report follows the defined project structure and describes the work progress in each Work Package and Task in detail.

2 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 WORK PACKAGE 1 – Data gathering and consolidation

Summary

The main goal of WP1 is to obtain suitable data for the description, assessment and screening of the Zar-3 pilot storage site. These data sources have been used as inputs during the development of a three-dimensional static geological model of the storage site and complex (WP2), dynamic modelling (WP3), risk assessment (WP6) and monitoring (WP7). The required data have been obtained from both publicly available sources (in particular CGS databases) and the archive and databases of the industrial Project Partners (and current Žarošice field operator) MND. All collected data have been consolidated and unified (Task 1.1). Task 1.2 was reserved for collection and analysis of well cores, no new cores were collected in 2023. The overview of all data is kept using a dedicated project geodatabase and GIS (Task 1.3). The work in WP1 was carried out by CGS (WP leader) and MND according to the plan.

Task 1.1 – Collection, consolidation and unification of existing data, site characterization

Main part of Task 1.1 has been completed in 2021. Nevertheless, collection, verification and consolidation of remaining input data continued in 2023 according to the needs of the other technical Work Packages (WP2-WP8), for example new data of well integrity logging on well ZA7. All maps, prepared in 2021 were updated, unified and uploaded to the project geodatabase (see Task 1.3).

Majority of the maps compiled in 2021 was part of the project result TO01000112-V3 (Set of thematic maps of the CO₂ Zar-3 storage site; type N_{map}). Maps were graphically and formally adjusted, unified and prepared to a final form. The result TO01000112-V3 was submitted in December 2023 and uploaded into TA ČR SISTA system. Fig. 2.1-1 shows the map of Land use as an example of updated and unified map, which is one of the maps from result TO01000112-V3.

The data described above, together with all additional data gathered, measured or otherwise established in the course of the project, are continuously stored in the project geodatabase (a spatial geodatabase in which geographical and spatial information are stored for future reference) that has been created as part of Task 1.3. To ensure that all project data share a unified geographic framework, a basic coordinate system (S42) was defined at the start of the project. All project data have been and will be converted to this system.

Task 1.1 has been carried out by CGS in cooperation with MND and finalized in December 2023 by creating the main result V3 – see above.

Fig. 2.1-1: Land use map of the wider area of Zar-3 CO₂ storage site.

Task 1.2 – Overview of available cores and their documentation, sampling selection

The goal of this Task is to access suitable core and cuttings materials in MND core repository for further analyses and take core samples needed for various laboratory experiments and tests (WP4, WP5).

During 2023, no new drilling cores were selected. The special “master table”, covering all selected core boxes and taken core samples, was updated. As a result, two separated “master tables” were created; one of them was arranged according to the “mother” well, the second “master table” was arranged according to the stratigraphy of cores. Tab. 2.1.-1 represents cut-out from the “master table” arranged according to “mother” well.

Tab. 2.1-1: Cut-out from the “master table” arranged according to the “mother” well.

Well name	Core No	Box No	Sample name (well_MD_C_B_from_to)	Sample X (S42)	Sample Y (S42)	Photograph
ZA6A	1	1	ZA6A_1929_1_1_50_65	3644275,16	5437366,08	
		2	ZA6A_1929_1_2_31_59	3644275,22	5437365,97	
		3	ZA6A_1929_1_3_80_90	3644275,32	5437365,76	
		4	ZA6A_1929_1_4_70_85	3644275,39	5437365,64	

Task 1.2 has been carried out by MND in cooperation with CGS.

Task 1.3 – Creation of a project geodatabase (database + GIS)

The project geodatabase, created by CGS in Task 1.3 in 2021, has been kept up-to-date in 2023 by continuous upload of data gathered in Task 1.1, as well as all other data gathered and created during realization of other WPs. All data designated for upload are verified, analysed and stored in the geodatabase for future use. In this way, the geodatabase is serving as the main project data source for all Work Packages. It is available online for all Project Partners, respecting, at the same time, the access rights, limited in some cases by the provisions of the Non-disclosure Agreement between MND and research partners of the project.

For selected spatial GIS data, an ArcGIS Online solution is available for presenting and sharing data with all Project Partners. In 2023, all maps created in frame of Task 1.1 were made available via ArcGIS Online. During 2024, spatial GIS data will be uploaded to the ZENODO repository according to the Data Management Plan.

No changes were made in the Data Management Plan in 2023.

Work in Task 1.3 has been carried out by CGS.

Deviations and changes

The work in WP1 has proceeded as planned.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Main results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
TO01000 112-V3	Set of thematic maps of the CO2 Zar-3 storage site	12/2023

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

2.2 WORK PACKAGE 2 – 3D geological model of the storage complex

Summary

All work in Work Package 2 was completed in 2022.

2.3 WORK PACKAGE 3 – Dynamic modelling and simulations

Summary

The main objectives of WP3 are to: (i) assemble and history match full-field reservoir model of the planned storage site, and (ii) simulate different options of CO₂ injection pilot while accounting for the most important effects related to CO₂ storage in fractured carbonate reservoirs.

The work within 2023 followed the work initiated in 2021 and continued in 2022. Sub-horizontal grid was used in 2022 version of simulation model. As presented in the Project meeting in Brno in December 2022, permeability distribution did not accurately match the PTA results. So it was decided not to continue in the history match improvement by using the sub-horizontal grid for property distribution (porosity, permeability) but using dipping grid orientation instead. Initially the dipping grid was used just for the property distribution but later it was decided using it as the simulation grid orientation as well. Chapter Task 3.4 gives more detailed description of the process.

Seismic monitoring study was carried out in 2023 as a part of WP7. The study required input from WP3, particularly CO₂ saturation changes during the pilot injection. Although the work on permeability distribution improvement was not finished and was continuing, history matched model to a certain extent was used as the seismic study input.

Similar results as used for the seismic monitoring study was used for CO₂ injection scenarios elaboration in WP8.

Requirement for using the dipping grid caused delays in achieving WP3 milestones and tasks. The M3.1 milestone had to be completed again with different grid geometry. The M3.2 and M3.3 milestones had not been officially completed but inputs for WP8 work were provided based on using the history matched model to a certain extent. Two versions of the CO₂ pilot injection were simulated: 1. - Injection into the ZA3 well after gas cap depletion and 2. - Injection into the ZA7 well before the gas cap depletion. The latter one seems to be more viable and is currently being used as the working version.

Main result V2 might be completed by the end of January 2024 after approving the final version of the history matched model between MND and NORCE. Peer-reviewed scientific article (V12 result) is being currently writing and hopefully finished in the middle of February 2024 and then submitted for the peer-reviewing process.

The work in WP3 was performed by MND (WP leader) and NORCE.

Task 3.1 – Import of upgraded 3D model and upscaling

Updated geological model using dipping grid instead of sub-horizontal was generated to more adequately accommodate uncertainties related to structure and petrophysical property distributions. Several permeability distributions were generated and upscaled in WP2. Afterwards they were imported into simulation model for testing in WP3. That iterative process was repeated several times required close and additional cooperation between the WP2 and WP3. The most suitable permeability distribution, that gave the most realistic water and/or gas production, was selected for further history matching process (see Task 3.4).

Task 3.2 – Dynamic data analysis to evaluate well-reservoir and fracture network parameters

The step-rate test was carried out on the 19th of December, 2023. Seismic stations were deployed in the field to monitor whether water injection caused any seismic events. Several injection periods, at different injection rates, were applied. Irrespectively of injection rate, no pressure increase was observed at the wellhead – even at the highest possible rate of 570 l/min = 820 m³/d. In total, 135 m³ of water was cumulatively injected through the whole process. Observed data will be analysed in 2024.

Task 3.3 – Upscaling of geochemical, geomechanical and compositional effects

The geomechanical studies in WP4 provided results that has been used in the simulation model. They were officially handed over from WP4 to WP3 in the beginning of 2023 (M4.1).

Transmissibility and pore volume multipliers serves as a direct input into ROCKTAB keyword in Eclipse simulator. By analysing reservoir rock samples, using the “Coreval 700” device at VSB, the relation between pore volume, permeability and hydrostatic stress was measured. In all 10 samples, with permeability more than 1 mD, was used to determine the multipliers to be fed into Eclipse.

In the experiments, the pore pressure was constant (2.7 MPa), while the confining pressure was increased in steps of 6.4 MPa till 45 MPa. By using the effective stress relation, $\sigma' = P_{conf} - P_{pore}$, the stress variation can be converted to pore pressure, assuming that it is *the effective stress* that drives deformation. As such, varying pore pressure is equivalent to vary the externally imposed tectonic stress.

By assuming constant tectonic stress, this enabled a coordinate shift from P_{conf} to P_{pore} . This defines the x-axis in Fig 2.3-1 and Fig. 2.3-2, below.

Further, by defining a reference pore pressure at 17.2 MPa, that was the pristine pore pressure of the field, the reference porosity (ϕ_{ref}) and permeability (k_{ref}) could be estimated from interpolation. As such, the transmissibility and pore volume multiplier could be defined by k/k_{ref} and ϕ/ϕ_{ref} , respectively. This represented the y-axis in Figure 1 and 2, and the measurements as function of the pore pressure coordinate could be plotted.

Only samples with a permeability exceeding 1 mD was selected from the 24 samples that was tested (see WP4 report). There are two reasons for this, being the extreme variation observed for the impermeable and low-porous samples, and moreover, their insignificant contribution to the flow in the field.

In the fractured carbonate case, it is likely that fractures and vugs dominate the overall flow dynamics in the field. As such, the data for transmissibility multiplier based on intact rock samples (solid line in Fig. 2.3-1) should be used with care for the overall flow simulations. On the other side, microfractures have been observed in thin sections, so that some of the fracture-dynamics could be included in the observed dynamics. The argument for using the transmissibility multiplier is that it is rooted in relevant rock samples from the field. It is however outside the scope of the work in WP4 to quantify the importance of larger fractures, and how fracture dynamics induce permeability dynamics in responds to pore pressure variation, even though this would be a useful task to undertake. Ideally, a field scale injectivity tests could resolve this issue.

Fig. 2.3-1: Transmissibility multiplier (k/k_{ref}) as function of pore pressure from the coordinate shift using the effective stress relation. The samples with well, core number and box ID are shown in the legend as well as the permeability and porosity at 17.2 MPa.

Fig 2.3-2: Pore volume multiplier (ϕ/ϕ_{ref}) as function of pores prssure obtained from the co-ordinate shift using the effective stress relation. In the legend, the samples are shown with well name, core and box number, as well as the permeability and porosity at 17.2 MPa.

Can we deplete to 2 MPa pore pressure – any geomechanical constraints?

In 13 of the 24 loading tests, the samples were not only loaded, but also unloaded, i.e., the porosity and permeability was measured also when the confining pressure was reduced. By comparing the porosity and permeability of the unloading to the loading path, one can identify to what extent irreversible damage has been accumulated in the sample due to loading. In all samples, except for one, the unloading paths were similar, implying that the reservoir samples withstood the imposed load. Thus, we may conclude that the hydrostatic strength of the samples exceeds 42 MPa effective stress (i.e., maximum of 45 MPa hydrostatic stress minus 2.6 MPa pore pressure). The value of 42 MPa is shown in Figure 3 that display the failure envelope of the Zar-3 reservoir rocks in qp -space. Here, $q = \sigma_1 - \sigma_3$, and $p = 0.5(s_1 + s_3) - \alpha_B P_{pore}$, and as such the hydrostatic stress is at $q = 0$. Since most of the samples withstood the hydrostatic stress, this implies that the hydrostatic failure envelope is to the right of 42 MPa (typically the hydrostatic failure is displayed as a parabolic equation – as exemplified by the dashed line in Fig. 2.3-3).

By estimating the field stresses from the weight of the overburden and the side stress from Poisson ratio and uni-axial strain assumption, the initial field stress at 1750 m depth can be determined. Some degree of uncertainty in the estimates are displayed as the green cloud of data in Fig. 2.3-3.

One of several possible reservoir development scenarios that is being evaluated, is a gas cap depletion to 2 MPa. The idea is to generate maximal space for the injected CO₂ after gas cap has depleted. The consequence of a depletion down to 0 MPa can be seen as the shift to the grey area in Fig. 2.3-3. As can be seen, the stress state at depletion is

The permeability distribution in the simulation model reported in the 2022 interim report, did not accurately match values from pressure transient analysis (PTA) (Task 3.2). As such, it was decided not to continue in the history match improvement by using the sub-horizontal grid for property distribution (porosity, permeability) but using “follow base” (i.e. dipping grid) orientation instead. The reason for the change was that using sub-horizontal grid for a dipping structure would not correctly reflect dipping continuity of the geological horizon in the reservoir. Initially, the dipping grid was used just for the property distribution and they were redistributed into the sub-horizontal grid and used in simulation for testing how good initial history match was achieved. But later it was decided using the dipping grid also as the simulation grid. The reason was the easier way of handling in the simulator when some editing was required.

The dipping grid, however, caused premature and excessive water and gas productions into the ZA3 well at the beginning of the production history that were not observed in the reality. To obtain the internal consistency between the geological observations, the production and pressure history, this entailed significant work. So, plenty of different permeability distributions, generated using various techniques and iterations in property modelling, were evaluated in WP2. The goal was to identify the most suitable one. Within the process a lot of short simulation runs (simulating a few first years of the production history) were realized in WP3. That iterative process was repeated several times required close and additional cooperation between the WP2 and WP3. The Gaussian sequential simulation was chosen as a property distribution method with anisotropic variogram distribution with the -45° rotation and 1425 m and 700 m search cone range in major and minor directions. Rather low nugget was chosen 0,05 to honour the higher variability close to the wells - see Fig. 2.3-4

Fig. 2.3-4: Example of simulation of property distribution.

Initial permeability distribution resulting from geological model (geomodel permeability) had to be adjusted in several steps and within plenty of simulation runs to

match results of the PTA. Permeability map resulting from the history match process is displayed in the Fig. 2.3-5.

Fig. 2.3-5: Permeability map resulting from the history match process.

Pressure match in the ZA3 observation well is illustrated in the Fig. 2.3-6:

Fig. 2.3-6: Pressure match in the ZA3 well.

The current version of the history matched model is being reviewed by NORCE and improved by MND according to NORCE's comments.

Task 3.5 – Design and simulations of pilot CO₂ injection

CO₂ injection into ZA3well after a gas cap depletion was assumed during the 2nd reporting period. Here, a new CO₂ injection scenario was defined during the 3rd reporting period where CO₂ is injected into the ZA7 well before the gas cap depletion. The advantage of this scenario is that the ZA7 well is currently being used as a produced water disposal well. So, it could with lower costs be prepared for a CO₂ injection, without the additional workover as would be the case for the ZA3 well. An additional advantage is that the ZA3 well can be used for monitoring during the pilot injection.

In the simulation, the injection of 120 tons of CO₂ per day and 70 thousand tons cumulatively during the pilot injection period within less than two years (i.e. 583 days) was simulated. In the scenario, CO₂ was injected into the water zone in the ZA7 well, by using the dipping grid geometrical model.

Fig. 2.3-7 illustrates CO₂ (solvent) saturation at the end of the pilot injection:

Fig. 2.3-7: CO₂ saturation at the end of the pilot injection.

Even not having finished the work on improving the property distributions, the history matched model to a certain extent was used as the input for WP8 and the Seismic monitoring study.

Deviations and changes

The change in grid geometry from horizontal to dipping, and the process to determine the best matching permeability distribution to PTA results, while at the same time ensuring a reasonable match with the observed production and pressure measurements caused significant work and delays in WP3. Remaining milestones and main results will be accomplished and delivered in 2024.

The M3.1 milestone had to be completed again with different grid geometry. The M3.2 and M3.3 milestones had not been officially completed but inputs for WP8 work were provided based on using the history matched model to a certain extent. Two versions of the CO₂ pilot injection were simulated: 1. - Injection into the ZA3 well after gas cap depletion and 2. - Injection into the ZA7 well before the gas cap depletion. The latter one seems to be more viable and is currently being used as the working version.

Main result V2 might be completed by the end of January 2024 after approving the final version of the history matched model between MND and NORCE. Peer-reviewed scientific article (V12 result) is being currently writing and hopefully finished in the middle of February 2024 and then submitted for the peer-reviewing process.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Main results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
TO01000 112-V12	Peer-reviewed scientific article presenting results of integrated approach to reservoir simulation of the Zar-3 field and pilot CO ₂ injection	Postponed to 04/2024

Milestones

Milestone	Date	Description
M3.2	Postponed to 01/2024	Transfer of history matched reservoir model upgraded to be capable of simulating CO ₂ injection scenarios to WP8
M3.3	Postponed to 01/2024	Transfer of the reservoir model and pilot simulation results for further use in WP8

2.4 WORK PACKAGE 4 – Geomechanical characteristics

Summary

The objective of WP4 has been to characterize geomechanical properties of the storage complex and assess how the injection of cold CO₂ impacts the safe operation envelope. The injection program is, amongst other cases, constrained by the mechanical reservoir stability. As the injection of cold CO₂ leads to thermal contraction *and* changes in the effective stresses, they will both contribute to a movement in the stress-space towards failure.

The remaining work of WP4 is to ensure the three papers (results V11, R4.4 and R4.5) to be published within April 2024. Two papers have been submitted, and the third paper is under progress of being written.

Task 4.1 – Geomechanical parameter determination of overburden and reservoir samples

The subject of the research in 2023 was to continue with geomechanical tests of rock samples from the mature oil and gas field Žarošice, which is located in the region of south-eastern Moravia. The location appears to be a suitable place for long-term storage of carbon dioxide emission gas due to the hydrodynamic closure of the horizon. Drill core samples were obtained from the deposit and geomechanical testing was carried out on them. The rock samples were modified to achieve a regular cylindrical shape. As part of the research, a combination of several testing methods is appropriate with the aim of comprehensive knowledge of the deposit and the creation of a model for CO₂ injection. A total of 6 new samples, taken from four wells, were tested.

Task 4.2 – Non-destructive determination of mechanical changes for samples exposed to CO₂

The mechanical-elastic properties were determined non-destructively using the UKS-14 measuring device from Geotron-Elektronik. This mobile device consists of an ultrasound generator producing impulses with a frequency of 20-350 kHz. The tested samples are fixed in the respective mechanisms, where one base of the cylinder-shaped sample is fixed on the so-called exciter, which emits ultrasonic waves, and the other base is fixed on the so-called sensor, which receives the excited ultrasonic waves. The tested sample must always be properly fixed so that it does not rotate and at the same time does not touch any edges of the measuring apparatus.

The results of the above-mentioned geomechanical testing are shown in Tab. 2.4-1. For better graphic clarity, the values in the individual columns of the graphic table are highlighted, according to this scheme:

Tab. 2.4-1: Results of measured values of mechanical-elastic, petrophysical and mechanical properties of rock samples

Sample ID	Por. (%)	Per. (mD)	Density (g·cm ⁻³)	v _p (km·s ⁻¹)	v _s (km·s ⁻¹)	v _{dyn} (-)	E _{dyn} (GPa)	G _{dyn} (GPa)	K _{dyn} (GPa)	Unc. comp. str. (MPa)	Pore compr. V _{pc} (MPa ⁻¹)	Bulk compr. C _{bc} (MPa ⁻¹)	Biot coeff. (-)
BH1	1,41	0,17	2,72	4,748	2,587	0,29	46,98	18,23	37,11	55,23	1,52E-03	3,45E-05	0,637
BH2/1	2,50	21,56	2,57	3,584	1,739	0,35	20,93	7,77	22,66		6,99E-03	2,17E-04	0,942
BH/2	3,77	12,93	2,49	2,838	1,236	0,38	10,50	3,80	14,96	3,09	1,12E-03	5,53E-05	0,773
BH3/1	2,79	1,22	2,55	4,516	2,224	0,34	33,76	12,60	35,15		2,16E-03	7,55E-05	0,834
BH3/2	1,61	1,50	2,69	4,830	1,638	0,44	20,72	7,22	53,14	61,98	4,81E-03	9,75E-05	0,871
BH4	3,63	0,58	2,73	4,639	2,135	0,37	33,99	12,44	42,17		2,62E-03	1,11E-04	0,887

It can be seen from Tab. 2.4-1 that, although samples from the same deposit and the same reservoir structure were tested, relatively significant differences in mechanical-elastic parameters are recorded. Graphical representation of dynamic modulus of elasticity (E, G, K) and speed of propagation of elastic waves, respectively. Poisson's numbers can be seen in Fig. 2.4-1.

The dependence (linear regression) between the speed of longitudinal and transverse waves can be seen in Fig. 2.4-2.

The different speed of elastic waves and the different values of mechanical-elastic parameters determined from it can be caused by the following factors:

- 1) Different mineralogical composition;
- 2) Different strength bonds (mechanical disruption of rocks, induced mainly by structural-tectonic processes);
- 3) Different porosity;
- 4) Different degree of saturation;
- 5) Anisotropy of rock samples.

Fig. 2.4-1: Graphical representation of dynamic modulus of elasticity (E , G , K) and speed of propagation of elastic waves, respectively Poisson's numbers.

Although rocks of the same petrographic type, taken from one deposit of the same reservoir structure, were tested as part of the research, relatively significant differences in the observed mechanical-elastic parameters are recorded. It was an effort to determine whether there is a dependence between mechanical-elastic parameters and other observed parameters of petrophysical and mechanical properties.

From the results presented, it is evident that there is a dependence in the form of linear regression for some monitored parameters. This is particularly the case with the dependence between porosity and the propagation speed of longitudinal waves, or volume mass and velocity of propagation of longitudinal waves. The respective graphs show the equations of linear regression in the form of a straight line, i.e. $y = k \cdot x + b$. The straight line k indicates the steepness of the straight line, i.e. how intensively the value of one parameter (longitudinal wave speed) decreases/increases on the other observed parameter (porosity, volumetric mass).

Linear regression equations of the dependence of porosity and velocity of propagation of longitudinal waves, obtained both by current and archival research (research of carbonate rocks), are presented in Table 2.4-2. Values of the slope k are graphically highlighted according to this scheme:

Tab. 2.4-2: Dependence (linear regression) between porosity (Por) and velocity of longitudinal waves (vP)

Linear regression	Value of reliability R^2	Guideline k	Archival research
$Por = -0,8475 \cdot v_p + 6,3043$	0,7399	-0,8475	Presented research
$Por = -6,348 \cdot v_p + 37,984$		-6,348	Sayed et al., 2015
$Por = -6,33 \cdot v_p + 39,293$		-6,33	
$Por = -4,733 \cdot v_p + 29,377$	0,884	-4,733	Kahraman and Yeken, 2008
$Por = -11,236 \cdot v_p + 59,7416$	0,46	-11,236	Assefa et al., 2003
$Por = -1,899 \cdot v_p + 15,24$	0,74	-1,899	Pappalardo, 2015
$Por = -0,719 \cdot v_p + 6,377$	0,6	-0,719	Pappalardo, 2015
$Por = -4 \cdot v_p + 3,1465$	0,85	-4	Kurtulus et al., 2016

It can be seen from Tab 2.4-2 that the presented research found a smaller angle of the guideline than what was found by archival research. However, it should be mentioned that the presented research examined samples with a low porosity range (1 to 4%).

Linear regression equations of the dependence of porosity and velocity of propagation of longitudinal waves, obtained both by current and archival research (research of carbonate rocks), are presented in Tab. 2.4-3. Values of the slope k are graphically highlighted according to this scheme:

Tab. 2.4-3: Dependence (linear regression) between bulk density (D_b) and velocity of longitudinal waves

Percentile			
10			90
Linear regression	Value of reliability R^2	Guideline k	Archival research
$D_b = 0,1054 \cdot v_p + 2,1827$	0,9708	0,1054	Presented research
$D_b = 0,27 \cdot v_p + 1,13$		0,27	Sayed et al., 2015
$D_b = 0,382 \cdot v_p + 0,446$		0,382	
$D_b = 0,213 \cdot v_p + 1,256$	0,821	0,213	Kahraman and Yeken, 2008
$D_b = 0,2316 \cdot v_p + 1,7384$	0,81	0,2316	Yasar and Erdogan, 2004
$D_b = 0,213 \cdot v_p + 1,256$	0,821	0,213	Kahraman and Yeken, 2008
$D_b = 0,28 \cdot v_p + 1,59$	0,934	0,28	Saskar et al., 2012
$D_b = 0,3 \cdot v_p + 0,9815$	0,8794	0,3	Kurtulus et al., 2016

As part of the research, geomechanical tests of carbonate rocks were carried out. The samples were taken from the reservoir structure of the Žarošice deposit. Potentially, the possibility of geosequestration of CO_2 into this reservoir structure is being considered. Geosequestration of CO_2 must be preceded by a series of geomechanical tests verifying the petrophysical and mechanical properties of the rocks.

Although carbonate rocks of practically identical mineralogical composition, taken from the same deposit and the same reservoir structure, were tested as part of the research work, relatively significant differences in the propagation speed of elastic waves, and therefore also in the mechanical-elastic characteristics, are recorded. Possible factors that may affect the propagation velocity of elastic waves have been interpreted. Using the values of petrophysical and mechanical properties (possible factors affecting the speed of propagation of elastic waves), it was determined whether there is a dependence between these properties and the speed of propagation of elastic waves. Linear regression relationships (equations) were established between porosity, resp. volume mass and velocity of longitudinal waves.

In the discussion, a comparison of the results of linear regressions of monitored dependencies, determined on the one hand by various authors who have conducted research on carbonate rocks in the past, and on the other hand determined by the presented research is made. The linear regression equations determined by the presented research are quite similar to those determined by other authors. However, it must be said that in the presented research, samples with a low porosity range were observed (approx. 1 to 4%, while other authors studied samples with porosity up to approx. 20%).

Task 4.3 – Field stress and strength determination at in-situ conditions, and the effect of cooling

In frame of Task 4.3, main result V11 is preparing (so called Paper 2) “Evaluation of safe operating envelope for CO₂ injection under variability and uncertainty in rock mechanical parameters and Earth’s stresses”

A paper was submitted the 11th December on the determination of the safe operational envelope. The analysis includes rock mechanical strength and thermal-elastic stiffness parameters combined with Earth stresses - all parameters subject to uncertainty. The uncertainty of the input parameters was quantified by probability density functions (pdf’s). Monte Carlo simulations were performed to draw from these pdf’s, and then to evaluate mechanical stability as function of temperature and pressure. As the injection of CO₂ cools down the reservoir this leads to thermal contraction which in turn reduces the minimum horizontal Earth stress. At the same time, the weight of the overburden can be assumed constant, thus increasing the deviatoric stresses. Moreover, as pore pressure increases by the injection of CO₂, the mean effective stress is in turn reduced. For each pore pressure and temperature, Monte Carlo simulations were performed to determine the likelihood of failure at each *P* and *T*. By systematically varying *P* and *T*, the safe operation envelope during CO₂ injection was evaluated 4 000 times, and the number of failed ‘cases’ could then be given calculated from the experimental and reservoir uncertainty. This complete work was submitted, as paper 2, to the Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control the 11th December 2023 (Nermoen, Shchipanov, Porzer, Sancer, & Berenblyum, 2023).

The work-flow has also been shared with the scientific community in:

- An earlier version of the same work was also presented as a poster at the Trondheim TCCS-12 in June 2023 (Nermoen, Porzer, Sancer, Shchipanov, & Klempa, 2023)
- The utilization of this data was also included in the work presented by E. Ford under WP6 (Ford, et al., 2023).
- The geomechanical work related to safe operation window during depletion, and how pore volume multiplier and transmissibility index multiplier, as output of WP4 work has been presented by M. Pagac (Pagac, et al., 2023) under WP3 to the GeoNet Forum.

Paper 2 was submitted under the delivery V11 “Peer-reviewed article on combined use of ultrasonic velocity and triaxial experiments in decision analysis for CO₂ storage projects”.

In frame of Task 4.3, another result R4.4 is preparing (so called Paper 1): “Geomechanical data base of rock samples from the Žarošice hydrocarbon and storage complex (South Moravia, Czech Republic): Petrophysics, stiffness, strength, and effective stress estimates for stability evaluations during CO₂ injection”

A paper was submitted the 26th October 2023 based on the geomechanical laboratory tests results aimed at determine mechanical stiffness and strengths of rocks samples represented in the Zar-3 storage complex. Moreover, thermal expansion coefficient and heat capacity was determined. Laboratory tests were performed on intact rock samples, as such, the results are prone to survival bias (i.e. only intact rock samples that withstood the coring, exhumation, storage and rock sampling was evaluated). The potential bias was discussed and methods for rock massifs adjustments were developed.

Moreover, conservative choices were made, in e.g., in the estimated Earth stresses. The rock-mechanical tests were reported at invariant stresses (in both $\tau\sigma$ and qp -space) enabling a direct comparison between rock strength and Earth stresses. The mechanical data from laboratory tests, and the estimates of Earth stresses were the focus of paper 1 that was submitted to Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control (Nermoen, Klempa, Porzer, & Sancer, 2023).

Task 4.4 – Uncertain input data leading to probabilistic faulting and fracturing estimate – maximal CO₂ injection pressure determination

Within this task, the results from previous tasks (T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3) were analysed. In 2023, the preparatory work of result R4.5 started (so called Paper 3): Bayesian statistics for hypothesis testing – Utilization of scattered, limited data sets

The influence of CO₂ on the geomechanical stiffness was measured on samples exposed to CO₂ over prolonged periods of time. Even though the samples display a univocal reduction in elastic stiffness, the variation in to what extent the samples softened is large, and the number of samples is limited. The data reported in Paper 1, display a correlation between elastic stiffness and rock mechanical strength of the reservoir rock. Paper 2 will quantify the effect of scattered data on the safe operation envelope.

Paper 3 focus on resolving hypothesis testing via a suitable statistical testing techniques. This is important because the potential chemical rock-fluid interactions may reduce the safe envelope. We are developing Bayesian statistical testing techniques for hypothesis testing. This is a technique tailored to cases with limited and scattered data.

This quantitative work is ongoing, and is the focus of the last paper to be reported in WP4. The aim is to complete this paper by February 2024 and is to be delivered under R4.5 “Peer-reviewed article on influence of CO₂ injection pressure limit on stability of reservoir rocks”.

Deviations and changes

The work in 2023 ran according to the plan and two papers were submitted. The ambition is that these papers are accepted within April 2024, but that depends on how the papers are being received by the Journal. The work package was led by NORCE, the papers were drafted by NORCE and reviewed by the VSB colleagues. Before the paper was submitted, they went through an internal round within the CO₂-SPICER consortium. The experimental work was conducted by VSB. The interpretation and analysis of the laboratory results was conducted by NORCE and VSB.

There are no major deviations in WP4 to report within the interim report, however, there is a chance that paper 3 will not be accepted within April 2024.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

Milestones

No milestones were planned for this reporting period.

2.5 WORK PACKAGE 5 – Geochemistry of rocks and fluids

Summary

The main outputs of the WP5 in 2023 include detailed characteristics of molecular and isotopic composition of rock extracts, oils and gases, their mutual correlation and making conclusions on the migration of fluids in the Zar-3 storage complex. The geochemical data are further used in experiments and modelling of fluid – rock interaction carried out by VSB in close cooperation with CGS, MND and NORCE.

Task 5.1 – Geochemistry of fluids

Geochemistry of oils

New analyses of molecular biomarkers in oil samples were made using gas chromatography GC-MS. Based on the density, viscosity, acid values, biomarkers and other properties the Zar-3 and reference oils are classified as medium sweet crude oils. Based on the chromatographic whole-oil analysis the ZA4A oil is composed of a heavily biodegraded black oil (C₁₅₊) mixed with a gasoline range light oil of very contrasting thermal maturity and alteration.

The black oil has almost no n-alkanes and the biodegradation in the Vranovice Fm. dolomite reservoir reached level of 6+ on the PM scale. Black oil correlates with the Mikulov Fm. source rocks and was generated at 110-140 °C. Thermal maturity of the black oil fraction is equivalent to vitrinite reflectance of 0.86%, which occurs in source rocks at depth of ca 5 km.

Gasoline range light hydrocarbons consist of a full range of n-alkanes, branched and cyclo-alkanes, which indicate a much lower biodegradation than the black oil. Majority of hydrocarbons in the gasoline fraction are quantified and the derived transformation and correlation ratios are calculated. Transformation in reservoir shows different steps of biodegradation of the gasoline range hydrocarbons from the first “victims” removed from the mixture (n-C7) to those more resistant “leftovers” (dimethylcyclopentane etc.). Additional alterations include water washing, which removes preferentially aromatic compounds, such as benzene (C₆H₆), toluene (C₆H₅CH₃) and xylenes (C₆H₁₀). Oils from Zar-3 and adjacent oil and gas fields are grouped based on the transformation ratios TR1 – TR8.

Multivariate statistical (UPGMA) analysis was used to evaluate similarities and differences among the light hydrocarbon fractions of the studied oils. Five genetic groups (families) were identified among the gasoline fraction of the oils in the region. ZA4A oil is most similar to UH57, UH19 and NIK2A.

Gas geochemistry

The produced gas from the Zar-3 wells has in average 82-86% methane and 5.1-10.4% carbon dioxide since field opening. Methane is purely thermogenic with no microbial contribution in Zar-3 (Fig. 2.5-1 and 2.5-2). Carbon dioxide originates from dolomite dissolution. The ZA8AH well samples represent a different type of gas, probably due to a long non-producing time interval and stratification of the gas column in the well.

Fig. 2.5-1: Zar-3 gas characteristics are shown in “Bernard” type plot based on $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CH_4) carbon isotopic composition of methane and $\text{C}_1/(\text{C}_2+\text{C}_3)$ dryness index from ZA3, ZA4a, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA14H and reference gas samples from the Uhřice, Dambořice (Jurassic and Carboniferous reservoirs) and Klobouky, Bošovice, Hostěradky, Násedlovice fields (Paleogene reservoirs).

Fig. 2.5-2: Genetic types of natural gas based on carbon $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (CH_4) and hydrogen (deuterium) δD (CH_4) isotopic composition of methane: ZA8H gas sample. Reference fields: MMF - microbial methyl type fermentation, MCR - microbial carbonate reduction, Thermal - thermogenic, Hy-thermal - hydrothermal geothermal (crystalline), Atm – atmospheric methane, Abio - abiogenic mantle methane.

In the broader neighbourhood microbial methane occurs but at shallower depth in Jurassic (Mil-1) and Carboniferous reservoirs (Nit-1, Kro-2 and Zda-131, Fig. 2.5-3).

H_2S started to occur at the annulus, probably due to introduction of sulphate reducing bacteria (SRB) into the reservoir during storage of the produced and separated formation water from the produced oil-gas-water suspension.

Fig. 2.5-3: Zar-3 gas characteristics based on $\delta^{13}\text{C}(\text{CH}_4)$ carbon isotopic composition of methane in respect to depth from ZA3, ZA4a, ZA6, ZA8H, ZA14H and reference gas samples from the Uhřice, Dambořice (Jurassic and Carboniferous reservoirs) and Klobouky, Bošovice, Hostěrádky, Násedlovice fields (Paleogene reservoirs). Microbial methane is observed in shallower Jurassic (Mil-1) and Carboniferous reservoirs (Nit-1, Kro-2, Uh-9 and Zda-131).

The soil gas samples contain CO_2 in the amount 0,146 - 7.188 %_{vol}, the carbon isotopic composition $\delta^{13}\text{C}-\text{CO}_2$ ranges from -21.7 to -14.5‰.

Geochemistry of formation water

Chemical analyses of formation water samples from Za-3 were completed in CGS, VSB and MND labs. Complete analytical results are stored in the project geodatabase. The data serve as a basis for the CO_2 -rock-water interaction experiments (Task 5.4) and modelling (Task 5.5), as well as for the reservoir modelling (WP3).

The formation water in the Zar-3 field is a typical marine, deeply buried water of Na-Cl type brine and low in bicarbonate ion HCO_3^- content. Activity of sulfate reduction bacteria (SRB) can be expressed by the following equation:

Hydrogen sulphide did not occur in the early produced oil and gas from tubing, indications are that it did occur in the annulus. Human activity probably contributed to later occurrence of H_2S (e.g. during storage of the produced formation water back in the aquifer and during workover).

Formation water mineralization in the reservoir, overburden and underburden rocks

Mineralization of pore water is controlled by the original depositional environment and secondary alterations due to fluid – rock interactions and infiltration of descending fresh water from the surface. Here the mineralization expressed as total dissolved solids (TDS) in water is shown in respect to true vertical depth (TVD sub sea) in the broader Zar-3 area of interest for the overburden caprocks, main reservoir and underlying formations (Fig. 2.5-4).

Overburden includes

- overthrust Ždánice unit with Ždánice-Hustopeče, Menilite and Němčice Fms.,
- autochthonous Paleogene – Nesvačilka Fm.

Reservoir

- Jurassic – Mikulov Fm. (mainly caprock with minor reservoir)
- Vranovice Fm. (main reservoir – dolomite)
- Nikolčice and Gresten Fms. (additional reservoir – dolomitic and quartz sandstone)

Underburden

- Carboniferous Myslejovice Fm. (sandstone/shale turbidites)
- crystalline basement, Devonian carbonates.

Fig. 2.5-4: Mineralization of formation waters in overburden, main reservoir and underburden strata of the broader region of Zar-3 storage site.

Task 5.2 – Microbial activity in the reservoir

The DNA analysis of the water sample taken in 2021 from the production well ZA4A, depth ca. 1800 m TVDSS, was completed and 28 families of Archaea and Bacteria were identified.

Both Archaea (primitive bacteria) and Bacteria were found to be present in the Zar-3 reservoir. Sulfur reducing Bacteria (SRB) are absolutely dominant in the water (Desulfobacteria, Desulfobulbia, Desulfovibronia and Spirochaetia, coupled with

oxidation of organic compounds from the oil. Hydrogen sulfate (H_2S), pyrite and CO_2 are the products of the sulfate reduction process. The process is much more energetically favourable than methanogenesis, which is rather suppressed in Zar-3.

Clostridia, Bacilly and Proteobacteria make another functional group on the site. These anaerobic or facultative anaerobic organisms break down larger organic compound through some fermentative or respiratory processes and produce smaller organic molecules, e.g. acetates, which may serve as food for the Methanomicrobia.

Among Archaea the Thermococci prevail together with thermophilic or hyper-thermophilic degraders of organic matter (Gammmaproteobacteria and Incertae Sedis) in oil and sediments. They produce smaller organic molecules, which may serve as food for methanogens (Methanomicrobia) and ammonia oxidizers. Methanomicrobia occur, however, in lower quantity. Ammonia oxidizers were also found in low numbers.

The microbiological picture of the Zar-3 site is similar to some examples described in the literature (e.g. Kotlar et al. 2011¹, Kirk et al. 2016²), with sulfates-reducing organisms dominating the sample. Availability of sulfates is controlled by the reservoir rock and formation water geochemistry.

The probability of throat clogging by growth of bacterial biomass and undesirable formation of H_2S may be suppressed by nitrate addition to the injection water. It should be mentioned, that using chemicals, such as nitrates or bacteriocides, to fight against H_2S also suppresses methanogenesis.

Task 5.3 – Geochemistry and mineralogy of rocks

The available core samples from deep wells at the Zar-3 represent only a limited depth interval. To characterize the entire profile of the Zar-3 reservoir, 121 drill cuttings were provided by MND in December 2022 (Fig. 2.5-5).

Fig. 2.5-5: Core and new cutting samples for geochemical analyses. Žarošice (ZA) well numbers are shown next to each well trajectory.

¹ Kotlar, H.K. et al. (2011): High coverage sequencing of DNA from microorganisms living in an oil reservoir 2.5 kilometres subsurface. *Environmental Microbiology Reports* 3(6), 674–681

² Kirk, M.F. et al. (2016): Interplay between microorganisms and geochemistry in geological carbon storage. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, Vol. 47, pp. 386-395

In 2023, they were analysed for chemical composition using elemental analysis of organic and inorganic carbon (TOC, TIC and calculated calcite or dolomite), Rock-Eval pyrolysis, clay mineral composition by powder x-ray diffraction. The results were uploaded to project geodatabase.

The geochemical profile in Fig. 2.5-6 based on elemental composition and Rock-Eval pyrolysis shows specific trends in rock properties. The overthrust Ždánice unit consists of deep water sediments, low in carbonates, intermediate in TOC and hydrogen index (HI). Menilite Fm. is exceptional in this interval with elevated carbonate minerals (probably marls of the Dynow Fm.), organic carbon and the highest HI indicating high source potential due to high algae content. Thermal maturity is low.

The Nesvačilka Fm. of Eocene age has higher calcareous component, very high TOC and elevated HI typical of coaly particles with contribution of planktonic algae. No striking change in thermal maturity is observed at the overthrust – autochthonous Paleogene boundary.

The main reservoir – Vranovice Fm. with probable Nikolčice Fm. in the lower part is built by dolomites with some clay impurities in the upper part. The formation is lean in sedimentary organic carbon. Elevated hydrogen index occurs in the lower part, most probably associated with precipitated solid bitumen from the oil impregnations.

Fig. 2.5-6: Calcite or dolomite content calculated from total inorganic carbon (TIC), total organic carbon (TOC), hydrogen index (HI) and thermal maturity index (T_{max}) in respect to depth (TVD SS) in ZA3 well profile.

The underlying Myslejojvice Fm. of Carboniferous age has very low carbonate content, probably due to deposition below CCD. Redeposited coaly fragments make the TOC elevated, HI indicates typically humic type of kerogen. Thermal maturity is markedly higher than the rest of the profile, probably due to erosion of the upper part of Carboniferous strata. That is why the porosity and permeability of the Myslejojvice Fm. is very low.

Mineral composition of rocks

Vranovice Fm., the principal reservoir, represents an end member lithology of almost pure dolomite. The Nikolčice Fm., which underlies the Vranovice Fm., is rich in dolomite but has also quartz and minor rock-building minerals, such as feldspars.

The underlying Carboniferous Myslejšovice Fm. is composed of almost pure siliciclastic rocks (shale, siltstone and sandstone). Overlying marls of the Mikulov Fm. show broad variety of mineral composition, little or minor dolomite, abundant calcite, siliciclastics, mainly clay minerals, and pyrite. Paleogene siltstones of the Nesvačilka Fm. are rich in pyrite and have variable carbonate content. The pre-experimental results are used, among others, for optimization of the experimental conditions of the fluid – rock interactions (Task 5.4).

Optical and electron microscopy

Reservoir and caprock characteristics were complemented by microscopy in translucent and fluorescent light. Reservoir samples are represented by Vranovice Fm. and Nikolčice Fm. rocks. **Vranovice Fm.** consists of **dolostones** with fine to coarse grain size, rarely also **oolitic limestones**. **Nikolčice Fm.** is represented mainly by **sandy dolostones**.

Majority of Vranovice Fm. consists of dolostones that have undergone multiple stages of dissolution (**karstification**), dolomitization, collapsing causing **brecciation** and dolomite cementation. This can be demonstrated on medium-grained dolomite breccias (therefore fully dolomitized and collapsed rock) with high **vuggy** porosity (Fig. 2.5-7).

Fig 2.5-7: Heavily brecciated dolomite in the Vranovice Fm. cemented by fine grain dolomite and residual bitumens in plain polarized light (left) and fluorescence (right).

Caprock microscopy: Layered silty sandstones to arkoses of Carboniferous **Myslejšovice Fm.** act as **bottom seal in Zar-3 storage complex**. The rock is composed of subangular grains of quartz, feldspar and rarely mica. The rock is affected by compaction (fitted and sutured contacts of grains). Feldspars are intensely altered to clay minerals or dissolved, forming modest interparticle porosity. Small compressed and elongated coal particles were observed in some sandstones. Fracture porosity is developed along stylolites. Rarely, bituminous matter impregnation was found in thin sections, exhibiting warm orange UV fluorescence.

First seal partly overlying the Vranovice Fm. reservoir is **Mikulov Fm.** Petrologically, the Mikulov Fm. rocks range from **marly wackestones** to (silty) carbonatic/dolomitic sandstones (Falkenstein Fm. in Austria). Overall the rocks are fine grained, with high amount of clay, subangular bioclastic detritus and (sub)rounded intraclasts and pellets. Alochems are partly leached and recrystallized, forming minor moldic porosity. Sediment is poorly sorted (bioclasts being considerably bigger than intraclasts and pellets). Bitumenous matter was scarcely recorded in fracture pores.

Second seal covering both Vranovice Fm. and Mikulov Fm. is represented by **Nesvačilka Fm. – Žarošice Mb.** siltstones. The siltstones and sandstones are often dolomitic (Fig 2.5-8 and 2.5-9). Upper part is **heterogeneous**, in grain composition and size, ranging from tens of microns up to several mm. Besides quartz, feldspars are present together with fossils and rare glauconite. The rocks are well cemented with isopachous dolomite cement (45 % of the whole rock is built by dolomite) and only non-communicating intergranular porosity remains. Lower part of the Nesvačilka Fm. is quite **fine grained** (below 200 μm), containing mainly quartz and feldspars. Quartz grains are often cracked, while feldspars are altered. Pore space is filled by clay, silt and rarely carbonate cement. Large coal particles up to several cm in size were observed in some core samples.

Fig 2.5-8: Dolomitic sandstone of the Nesvačilka Fm. (left) is cemented by isopachous dolomite cement with remains of interparticle porosity (right).

Fig. 2.5-9: Sandy siltstone, Nesvačilka Fm. abundant oil impregnation (orange fluorescence) ZA4, TVDSS 1573 m.

Reservoir and caprocks samples impregnated by blue epoxy resin were analysed using image analysis. The relative area of open pores in a selected thin section area corresponds to optical porosity. The interpreted pore size distributions suggest, that in all rock types the microporosity prevails. In **reservoirs** an important contribution to the reservoir total porosity of cavernous and fracture pores with diameter ranging from 100

to 300 μm exists. The **caprocks** have about 5-10 times lower porosity than the reservoir rocks and have the majority of pores in the clay size ($<5 \mu\text{m}$) diameter (microporosity).

Bitumens in reservoir and caprocks and their correlation

Extractable organic matter in rocks (bitumens) was analysed using biomarker technologies by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Selected parameters were evaluated evidencing the type of biological origin, depositional environment and thermal maturity. The same data were analysed in all sedimentary formations and oils in Zar-3 storage complex and broader vicinity. Mutual comparison was made of rocks and fluids and conclusions were drawn on fluid migration in the eastern Bohemian Massif below the West Carpathians.

The diagenetic processes and thermal maturation with depth is currently extended by numerous data from the Zar-3 broader area. The principal biomarker groups include triterpanes (hopanes), steranes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and their alkylated homologues (phenanthrenes). At shallow depth the parameters reflect the biological configuration. With increasing depth and temperature the molecules change to more geological form. The diagenetic and catagenetic trends of the source rocks are shown in Fig. 2.5-10 based on the deep well core samples affected by oil migration as well as those not affected. Jurassic source rocks of the Mikulov Fm. show a very similar trend of thermal maturation to the Paleogene (Těšany and Nesvačilka Fms.) ones. The $22S/(S+R)$ C₃₁ hopane ratio and $20S/(S+R)$ C₂₉ sterane ratio start at lower values in the thermally immature interval and reach the oil generation window with values of 0.5-0.6 (hopanes) and 0.45-0.55 (steranes). In the same diagrams oil samples are shown with higher hopane and sterane values of. Thermal maturity is also measured by the methylphenanthrene index MPI₂, where Jurassic and Paleogene source rocks show parallel trends with depth, the Jurassic being slightly deeper.

The general conclusion based on Fig. 2.5-10 is, that all the source rocks are markedly less mature than the oils down to depth of 4 km and become similar at 4-5 km and more. In the Paleogene caprock the given thermal maturity parameters indicate infiltration of the same oil as occurs in the reservoir, but the oil is not movable (producible) as it is trapped in the micropores.

Numerous caprock samples in Zar-3 are **impregnated** (stained) **by migrated oil**, while the unaffected rocks, which occur further away from Zar-3, are of contrastingly lower maturity. This applies for the reservoir and partly also for the Nesvačilka Fm.

Multivariate statistics was applied to visualise the correlation of rock bitumens and oils in the broader Zar-3 area. Principal component analysis (PCA) of 10 biomarker ratios sensitive to depositional environment in 60 rock and 26 oil samples were identified.

Fig. 2.5-10: 22S/(S+R) C₃₁ hopane ratio and 20S/(S+R) C₂₉ sterane ratio in Jurassic (blue squares) and Paleogene rocks (orange crosses) and oils (green circles).

The samples form 3 major genetic groups:

Group 1 includes all oils, all reservoir samples in Zar-3 and deeper Jurassic source rocks (Mikulov Fm.). Some of the second seal (Nesvačilka Fm.) belong also to this group.

Group 2 represents Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm. away from migration pathways and secondary impregnation by oil (Kar-1). It does not correlate with any of the oils.

Group 3 includes Paleogene, Jurassic and Carboniferous rocks (Myslejovice Fm.), which are also not impregnated by oils and which do not correlate with any of the oils.

The interpretation is that the regional oil and gas migration in the eastern margin of the Bohemian Massif occurred since Middle Miocene, i.e. past 16 Ma. Migration took place at least 4-6 km vertically and 15-20 km horizontally below the West Carpathian fold-and-thrust belt. In this context it is not surprising that majority of the sedimentary formations were exposed to migrating fluids. Oil & gas accumulation formed in the dolomite reservoir of the Vranovice Fm. in the Zar-3 structure. Overlying Mikulov Fm. acts as efficient caprock. Paleogene Nesvačilka Fm. is partly impregnated by bitumens genetically related the reservoir oil but the impregnations are diffusive in their nature and bitumens are trapped in micropores. The overlying thrust plane of the Ždánice unit together with shaly Nĕmčice Fm. act as efficient seal and make even the Nesvačilka Fm. a good caprock.

The general conclusion is, that the Zar-3 storage complex is efficiently sealed and will be a **safe storage site**.

Task 5.4 – Experiments on CO₂– rock – fluid interactions and a predictive model

The year 2023 was focused on simulating chemical processes in CO₂–rock–brine systems in a pilot CO₂ storage in the Žarosice area (South Moravia, Czech Republic).

Models involving kinetic transport through porous media and thermodynamic aspects of multiphase systems are very useful in forecasting the impact of CO₂ injections on the changes to the rock environment at the site. These models are based on information regarding petrophysical, mineralogical, and hydrogeological characteristics of porous media, hydrochemical analysis of fluid composition, pressure and temperature conditions of the reservoir, and kinetic parameters.

Data and outputs, from laboratory experiments carried out in the laboratories of the Department of Geological Engineering at VSB – Technical University of Ostrava and data received from partners within the project, were used for modelling. These were mainly mineralogical, petrographic, geochemical, and hydrogeological characteristics of reservoir and cap rocks and the composition of brine as a reaction solution.

The results of geochemical modelling are the outputs of equilibrium and kinetic modelling of the geochemical reactivity of the CO₂–water–rock system, determining the influence of CO₂ on the porosity.

Kinetic and thermodynamic models were applied using The Geochemist's Workbench (GWB) Release 6.0. The findings from the modelling are as follows. Immediately after injection, CO₂ diffuses in its supercritical form and partially dissolves in the formation water. This process significantly changes the mineralogical, hydrogeological and geochemical conditions in the reservoir. It acidifies the original brackish formation water. It changes the mineralogical composition of the reservoirs and caprocks of the storage complex. Further, it causes chemical changes in the cement plugs and behind casing cementation in the wells. All these reactions present a potential risk in the CO₂ storage process in the selected structure and can lead to CO₂ leakage from the storage to the surface.

CO₂ solubility decreases with increasing temperature and molarity of the solution, while CO₂ solubility increases with increasing pressure. In the model the dissolution was carried out until the thermodynamic equilibrium was reached and the solution was saturated with CO₂. Based on the input parameters used in the PHREEQC model (brackish water ZA4A chemistry, P_{CO₂} = 150 bar, and temperature = 53 °C), we report the theoretical acidification of brackish water ZA4A as a result of CO₂ injection and calculated chemistry. The HCO₃³⁻ ion is the dominant carbonate component in the solution at alkaline pH. When the pH drops to the acidic values, the bicarbonate ions decrease in solution and carbonic acid, respectively, and CO₂(aq) becomes the dominant carbonate component.

The models were created in the first step for the **acidification** of the original solution at the desired CO₂ pressure ($f_{\text{CO}_2} = 70$ bar), then for the first six months of CO₂ injection into the structure and the last model for the degassing processes in reservoir and caprocks. The models are valid for a homogeneous pore medium with 100% saturation of the pore with brine solution at a constant injected amount and pT conditions in the reservoir. The injected amount of CO₂ is assumed to be 8750 t_{CO₂}/year, which corresponds to an injection rate of 0.28 kgCO₂/s.

For all rock samples, the most important chemical processes are the **dissolution of carbonates** (calcite and dolomite) and microcline due to acidification of the brackish water during the injection of CO₂ into the structure. Other chemical processes that the models describe include the **precipitation of magnesite**, which replaces dissolved dolomite completely, and the formation of **secondary carbonates** as a result of the increasing pH of the formation water in the structure over a longer period of time after injection is ceased. Carbonate minerals bind CO₂ to their structure and help to stabilize the pH of the brackish water after injecting. The consequence of this process is, however, the reduction in the porosity of the reservoir rock. In the long term, these processes are desirable. The formation of secondary phases is considered useful during the relaxation period of the storage complex after CO₂ injection. The newly formed phases trap the injected CO₂ in the structure and thus contribute to the stability of the rock environment.

Experiments with rock samples in the reaction chamber also confirmed the following. Immediately after its injection, CO₂ spreads in its supercritical form and partially dissolves into the formation water. This process significantly changes mineralogical, hydrogeological, and geochemical conditions at the storage site. It acidifies the original groundwater of the brackish water type; it can influence hydrogeological parameters, especially the porosity and permeability of the deposit rock; it changes the mineralogical composition of the deposit rock and can mineralogically affect the confining layers in the overburden. All these reactions can be a potential risk for the CO₂ storage process in the selected structure. It is therefore necessary to understand the mechanism of these reactions and to quantify and evaluate them to ensure the safety and sustainability of storage.

Task 5.5 – Evaluation of changes in reservoir properties during and after CO₂ injection

Interactions of the CO₂–rock–brackish water were studied using the Geochemist's Workbench (GWB) program for Jurassic dolomite reservoir rock and Paleogene and Carboniferous caprocks. The aim was to characterize the influence of CO₂ in the geological structure on mineralogical rock changes from the potential storage site.

Models of pH and **porosity** development during and after CO₂ injection were implemented in the GWB program (Figs. 2.5-11 to 2.5-13). The input parameters were the porosity data of samples ZA4A 8%, ZA4 0.886% and UH16 1.154%, the specific resistance of the brine in the reservoir is 5Ωm, the fugacity $f_{\text{CO}_2} = 70$ bars, the original pH of the brine 7.1 and the temperature 53°C.

Fig. 2.5-11: Changes in pH in the formation water and reservoir porosity during the first 2 hours after CO₂ injection.

Fig. 2.5-12: Changes in pH in the formation water and reservoir porosity during the first 2 hours after CO₂ injection.

Fig. 2.5-13: Changes in pH in the formation water and reservoir porosity during the 500 years after CO₂ injection.

The model evolution of porosity in caprocks is as follows:

1. The **reservoir** porosity decreases by 1.1% during the first model period. During 6 months of injecting, the porosity stagnates and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity increases by 0.6%. The original value of the reservoir rock porosity was 8% and the final value after the 500 relaxation years was 7.586%.
2. The porosity of the overlying **Paleogene (Nesvačilka Fm.) caprock** slightly increases during the first model period (acidification of formation water). The porosity of Paleogene caprock during the second model step slowly decreases and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity decreases to the original value 0.882%.
3. The porosity of underlying **Carboniferous caprock (Myslejovice Fm.)** slightly decreases during the first model period (acidification of brackish water). The

porosity of Carboniferous caprock during the second model step slowly increases and after 500 years of structure relaxation the porosity increases to the value 1.162%.

Deviations and changes in WP5

The analytical works were slightly delayed because of delay in providing additional core and cuttings samples (mainly from caprock) by MND because of tornado damaging the core repository at Lužice. Additional caprock and core samples analyses were carried out before the end of 2023. In general, the WP5 has achieved the planned results.

WP5 results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R5.2	Report and dataset: Chemistry of fluids	11/2023
R5.3	Report and dataset: Geochemical and microbiological evidence of archea-bacterial activity, methanogenesis and pore throats clogging of the reservoir	12/2023
R5.4	Report and dataset: Geochemistry of reservoir rocks and caprock	12/2023

Milestones

No milestones were planned for 2023.

2.6 WORK PACKAGE 6 – Risk analysis

Summary

The main objective of the work package is to assess leakage risks related to CO₂ storage in the Zar-3 hydrocarbon field and to compile the findings in a risk assessment report. Throughout the year, work has mainly focused finalizing leakage simulations of abandoned wellbores and caprock, and subsequently use the results in conjunction with local meteorological conditions to simulate gas dispersion to assess possible exposure and effects. As a central part of this work, a identification of main risk receptors within the area of interest was evaluated. Two workshops were held during the year: a virtual meeting in February and a physical meeting in Trondheim in June. A poster was presented at the Trondheim CCS conference in June titled “*Decision-making under uncertainty – case study from a Czech Republic CO₂ storage*”. The project and work performed for WP6 was also briefly presented at the ESRA Norway seminar [Status for risk and reliability methods – What are the research topics in Norway](#).

Throughout the year, work was performed by NORCE (WP leader), CGS and MND.

Task 6.1 – Hazard characterisation

By and large finalized during 2022, there were some additional parts added to this task in 2023, mainly as part of finalizing the draft report of WP6. This included assessments of blowout magnitude, duration and volumes. There was also an additional activity to re-log well ZA7, which main findings concluded that the status of the well, based on logging indicated that the well barriers remained intact. This conclusion was supported by CGS work on soil gas monitoring of southern and northern well hubs, which gave no indications of elevated levels of methane nor total petroleum gases at any of the monitoring points.

Fig. 2.6-1: Monitoring points for southern (left) and northern (right) well hubs.

Task 6.2 – Exposure assessment

The starting point for the exposure assessment is probability distributions of CO₂ and CH₄ leakage rates per well. A Monte Carlo simulation framework was used for simulating gas dispersion, and for determining gas concentration at locations for given risk receptors. 10 000 iterations have been used in the Monte Carlo simulation.

For each iteration, a random abandoned well is drawn, and the leakage rate is sampled from this well’s leakage rate probability distribution. The dispersion of gas depends in part on local meteorological conditions, in particular wind speed, wind direction and cloudiness. Recent historical meteorological data was obtained³ and compiled to establish probability distributions for these parameters, shown in Fig. 2.6-2. This data set is based on measurements from the area of interest between 01.06.21 and 11.05.22.

Fig. 2.6-2: Local meteorological data collected and converted to probability distributions, showing wind speed (left), wind direction (middle) and cloud proportion (right), for the area of interest.

The compiled meteorological data shows a mean wind speed of 3,4 m/s, ranging from 0 – 13,9 m/s, most likely wind directions being WNW, NNE and SE, and a mean cloud proportion of 46%. Gas dispersion was calculated using the Gaussian plume model and focusing on ground level concentrations.

Risk receptors that have been considered for the area of interest are shown in Tab. 2.6-1.

Tab. 2.6-1: Risk receptors for the area of interest.

Type	Instances
Humans	Žarošice residential area (population: 1100)
	Uhřice residential area (population: 750)
	Archlebov residential area (population: 871)
	Site operators
Animals	Bats
	Birds
	Frogs/Toads
	Lizards

³ *meteo_condition.xls*

Type	Instances
	Otter
	Bugs
	Polecat
	Butterflies
	Squirrels
Vegetation	Plants
	Flowers
	Trees
Surface water	Vápenka stream
	Zdravá voda
	Klasovsky potok
	Malénský potok
	Spálený potok [west & east]
	Trkmanka
Infrastructure	Roads
	Main/local water supply
	Storage site
	Wastewater plants (4)
	Residential areas

Relevant animal species, vegetation, and infrastructure to include have been determined based on CO₂-SPICER Report R1.2 “Report on pedology, geology, geomorphology, climatology, conflict of interest and nature protection“ (Janderková, Sedláček, Krejčí, Kolečka, 2022) and the document *zarosice_protected_species.xls* (Vácha, 2023), which lists species under EU and/or Czech law protection and reported sightings in or around the greater area of interest.

Simulated CO₂ ground level concentrations for the area of interest are shown in Fig. 2.6-3 for leakage from abandoned wellbores, indicating no overlaps between dispersed CO₂ and risk receptors.

Fig. 2.6-3: Simulated CO₂ ground level concentrations based on leakage from a random abandoned wellbore.

The polygons surrounding the abandoned wellbores represent CO₂ concentrations levels where green = [0-5000 ppm] (yellow = [5000-50000 ppm] and red \geq 50000 ppm are not visible due to no simulations yielding such ranges). Exposure to CO₂ levels exceeding 5000 ppm would on this basis only be conceivable in the immediate surrounding of a leaking abandoned wellbore, combined with gas becoming trapped in a confined space. Furthermore, there no simulated scenarios where the specially protected areas are exposed to elevated levels of CO₂. Based on sampling from all abandoned wells, the CO₂ concentration versus distance from release point is shown within the 10th and 90th percentiles in Fig. 2.6-4.

Fig. 2.6-4: Simulated CO2 concentration range (P10-P90 values) across all abandoned wellbores, for increasing distance from point of release. Concentration values are net contribution from release and do not include ambient levels.

Task 6.3 – Effects assessment

Exposure threshold levels have been reviewed based on literature studies for CO₂, and where available, for CH₄ (scarce). For humans (and most animals), CO₂ concentration levels at < 5000 ppm would yield low health impacts, < 50 000 ppm would yield moderate effects and > 80 000 ppm serious effects. Plants generally have higher threshold levels. The risks from methane primarily relate to explosive nature due to it being highly flammable. From a human health point of view, very high levels (>80% of air) could be fatal, though there are not many published sources on threshold levels.

Based on the dispersion simulations, proximities of risk receptors and local conditions, net CO₂ concentration contributions from the most likely leakage scenarios, from abandoned wellbores, is in the region of 5 000 ppm. This would occur only very close to point of release (< 10 m) and for site operators (not residential areas). To pose a risk to health would require gas becoming trapped/confined and presence of receptors at particular location over prolonged duration. The probability of occurrence for leakage from an abandoned wellbore is believed to be in the region of 10⁻³-10⁻⁴ in a long-term perspective.

Task 6.4 – Risk characterisation

The work performed in tasks 6.1-6.3 were presented in a holistic manner to reflect overall findings from the risk assessment. This involved assessments of likelihood of occurrence for different long- and short-term leakage scenarios, mapping likelihoods

and potential consequences in a risk matrix, proposing risk-reducing (both preventive and mitigating) measures, and highlighting the main uncertainties of the assessment.

Within Task 6.4, the final Risk assessment report (main result V4) covering all work of WP6 has been prepared.

Deviations and changes

There were no deviations and changes in 2023.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Main results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
TO01000 112-V3	Set of thematic maps of the CO ₂ Zar-3 storage site – joint result of WP1, WP6, WP7 and WP8	12/2023
TO01000 112-V4	Risk assessment report	12/2023

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R6.4	Well integrity logging	12/2023

Milestones

Milestone	Date	Description
M6.2	achieved 03/2023	Completion of hazard characterisation
M6.3	achieved 06/2023	Completion of exposure and effects assessment
M6.4	achieved 10/2023	Completion of risk characterisation

2.7 WORK PACKAGE 7 – Monitoring

Summary

The main objective of this WP is to prepare a storage site monitoring plan in the sense of Section 9 of the Act No. 85/2012 Sb. on the Storage of Carbon Dioxide in Natural Underground Geological Formations.

All Project Partners were involved under the leadership of CGS as WP leader. The main effort in 2023 was focused on the completion and finalization of the baseline atmogeochemical monitoring (last 3 campaigns in 2023), monitoring of natural seismicity and monitoring of induced seismicity during the Injection Step-Rate test (postponed from 2022), completion of the shallow groundwater monitoring (last 2 campaigns in 2023), shallow groundwater modelling and expected results preparation.

The work was generally performed according to the plan with some deviations (see chapter Deviations and changes). The status of the results to be delivered in 2023 is:

- Joint main result **V3** of WP1, WP6, WP7 and WP8 **Set of thematic maps of the Zar-3 storage site** (Nmap) – maps from WP7 were created and delivered.
- The other result **R7.8 Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring** postponed from 2022 to 2023 was created and delivered.
- The other result **R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results** was created and delivered.
- The other result **R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring** was created and delivered.
- The other result **R7.6 Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring** (deadline 3/2023) is postponed to 03/2024 due to the Injection Step-rate issues.

Task 7.1 – Methods and data

The sub-contract result of **R7.8 Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring** to assess the applicability of seismic survey – the most powerful monitoring tool for mapping the extension of the CO₂ plume in the subsurface – was successfully completed. Original deadline of 12/2022 was postponed to 11/2023 to allow for utilisation of the new 3D geological model of the storage complex as input.

This report is based on the existing seismic data from the site and available geological and petrophysical information, and combine them with forward modelling and creation of synthetic seismograms. Various seismic techniques like surface 3D, VSP (incl. 3D-VSP) or cross-hole were evaluated.

The study was subcontracted – seismic exploration expert Mr. Roman Pevzner (Perth, Australia) has been chosen as subcontractor as a result of competitive tendering. CGS took care of the procurement and realization, the technical support was utilized by MND.

Task 7.2 – Atmogeochemical monitoring

Atmogeochemical monitoring belongs to the group of basic monitoring methods used for all terrestrial CO₂ storage sites. The main aim is to determine the areal distribution of important soil gas components (CO₂, CH₄, O₂ and TP – total petroleum), and identify and monitor anomalies (if any), based on (1) periodical and (2) continuous soil gas monitoring.

In 2023, the result **R7.3 Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results** was created and delivered. The report summarizes the atmogeochemical monitoring in the Zar-3 pilot CO₂ storage complex including a brief introduction to the characteristics of the land use and pedology. Detailed baseline soil gas monitoring above the field was performed to determine potential soil gas anomalies, soil gas distribution and to improve the knowledge of the seal efficiency. The results will serve as a background for the future monitoring measurements during and after the true CO₂ storage making it possible to identify newly formed anomalies, if any. The experience learned during the baseline soil gas monitoring will serve as a basis for the main result of **V5 Site monitoring plan** prepared in 2024 in Task 7.5 as well.

In 2023, last 3 periodical monitoring campaigns were performed – in winter (February), spring (May) and summer-autumn (September) – using the same monitoring grid of 95 monitoring points defined at the beginning of the project (Fig. 2.7-1). At each point, the soil gas composition was measured by CGS, using the Ecoprobe-5 portable instrument from 80 – 100 cm deep drilled holes. Since the majority of the area is cultivated fields, it was not possible to prepare more monitoring campaigns in the spring-autumn period due to the field crops and harvest campaigns.

Fig. 2.7-1: Area map with the grid of 95 monitoring points (black dots) used for the periodical monitoring and positions of five IGS permanent atmogeochemical probes (orange dots) used for continuous monitoring. Left: detailed view of the Zar-3 field (yellow polygon) and protected deposit area (cyan polygon) with production licence areas (green rectangles); right: overview of the area of interest (red rectangle).

For the purposes of field data interpretation, weather conditions, in particular temperature, atmospheric pressure and rainfalls total have been collected and stored. During all 3 campaigns in 2023, 25 calibration soil gas samples were collected for laboratory chromatographic analysis. Atmogeochemical contour maps of the site area showing content of selected components in soil gas (CO_2 , CH_4 , O_2 and TP – total petroleum) and its changes with time are the main outcome of this work. An example is provided in Fig. 2.7-2 where the distribution of CO_2 in soil gas of all 8 monitoring campaigns (2021-2023) is shown. The monitoring campaigns were carried out in the same period (season) of individual years for the correlation purposes.

Fig. 2.7-2: average CO_2 content in soil gas in all 8 monitoring campaigns (2021 – 2023) with comparable CO_2 in soil gas patterns highlighted.

Content of CO_2 in soil gas measured by permanent probes (Fig. 2.7-3) provide much more detailed data set with trend of spring increase, summer maximum, autumn decrease and winter minimum observed in periodical monitoring. Unfortunately, 1 probe broke down in May 2023. The measured annual maximum CO_2 content in soil gas was up to 9 %_{vol} in summer 2021 but only up to 6 %_{vol} in 2022 and 2023 (Fig. 2.7-3). The differences are interpreted as a result of vegetation and microbiological activity related to the weather conditions (Fig. 2.7-4). Strong increase in CO_2 in soil gas correspond to the period after strong rainfalls (labelled in Fig. 2.7-4). All the permanent probes have been placed in grasslands to exclude the potential effects of the land use and soil devolatilization. The differences among the trends measured by individual permanent probes (shown in colours in Figs. 2.7-3 and Fig. 2.7-4) are primarily caused by different soil types, water table level and vegetation in situ. The highest values (green line in Figs. 2.7-3 and Fig. 2.7-4) were observed in the valley floodplain with

clayey low permeability on top of the soil profile. The lowest CO₂ values were observed on hilltops in more sandy soils.

Fig. 2.7-3: Time plot of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by permanent probes. For probe locations see Fig. 2.7-1. Timing of the periodical monitoring campaigns (usually 3-4 days) are marked by blue pointers. The black trend line represents weekly moving average of all stations.

Fig. 2.7-4: Time plot of CO₂ content in soil gas measured by permanent probes compared by the most important weather conditions factors – precipitation / rainfall total, atmospheric pressure and atmospheric temperature.

Task 7.3 – Seismic monitoring

Seismic monitoring is another representative of basic monitoring methods used for all CO₂ storage sites onshore. In 2023, the GFU team continued the operation of the permanent site seismic network consisting of 5 monitoring stations (Fig. 2.7-5), which are in operation since August/September 2021. According to the modified plan, the monitoring was terminated by the end of June 2023. As the stations recorded data in off-line mode, the measured data were processed in consecutive months. After the pre-processing (data downloading and reformatting), the same two step procedure as previously was applied: (1) by preliminary automatic picking and (2) by manual detailed interpretation of relevant seismograms.

Fig. 2.7-5: Map with positions of the permanent and temporal seismic monitoring networks in the Zar-3 area.

Both monitoring and data processing ran continuously during 2023 operating period as well as the whole campaign without any principal issues. The final 2023 seismic bulletin version based on the Zar-3 monitoring network measurements was finalised before the end of the year and the finalisation of the whole bulletin started immediately. It is expected to be finalized at the beginning of 2024.

Events observed in the region close to the Zar-3 area are shown in Fig 2.7-6. The potentially local events were identified with quarry blasts, from quarries which are located close to the Zar-3. Regularly, there are recorded also events from partly distant areas as Ostrava/Paskov or Lubin (Poland). The pronounced earthquake from Turkey (February 6th, 2023) with magnitude of 7.8 was detected as well.

During the data processing, the periodically repeated event occurred at 01:59 UTC were identified as an artefact caused by accidental coincidence of GMS status messages sent automatically (with small time drift) by autonomous network stations. The list of these artefact will be attached to the final report **R7.7 Data set and report with results of seismic monitoring** (deadline 4/2024).

Fig. 2.7-6: Seismic events observed in the region close to Zar-3 area – preliminary partial results with location of closest quarries labelled. Some of the newly detected events are located near the Dobrá Voda site in Slovakia and near the Austrian-Slovakian border.

In addition to the planned activity, a temporal seismic network of 11 seismic stations was installed and put in operation in Dec 2023 / Jan 2024. History of this temporal network is rather weird. This network was planned to enlarge the network detection ability during the planned Injection Step-Rate Test (SRT, see WP3 for details). The aim was to add temporal stations to monitor induced seismicity during the test itself and to detect events related to potential cracks opening, spreading etc., which cannot be generally retrieved from the 5 permanent network stations records. This temporal network was partly supported from the Project funds which were spared mainly during COVID period (no travel expenses) and cheaper operation of permanent network. Unfortunately, the SRT was cancelled twice for technical reasons just a few days before its planned start and the effort related to deployment of additional seismic stations has gone to waste. The third term for SRT was planned for Dec 2023 and the temporal seismic network was deployed. As the permanent network is not in operation (see above), we had to deploy 11 stations this time: 6 at the position of previous temporal network and 5 at the position of (previous) permanent network. The station de-deploying is planned for the very beginning of 2024.

Task 7.4 – Shallow groundwater monitoring

The shallow groundwater monitoring is essential for both understanding the shallow groundwater regime on the site, and establishing a baseline for subsequent monitoring of groundwater quality in later stages of site development. This Task is executed by CGS and VSB. The other result **R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring** is postponed to Jan/Feb 2024 due to the task leader change issue.

From 2021 to 2023, the shallow hydrogeological monitoring campaigns were performed by CGS in March, June, October and December to cover all seasons of the year. In 2023, the campaigns were performed in March and October only. The groundwater level (m), spring yield (l/s), electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), pH (-) and water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) have been monitored. From the beginning, 19 monitoring points/objects (Fig. 2.7-7) were monitored. Those are e.g. shallow wells, boreholes and springs. Unfortunately, access to 3 original monitoring points was not possible in 2022 nor in 2023 due to various reasons, such as new fence construction or the frozen borehole lid in winter.

Fig. 2.7-7: Position of 19 original groundwater monitoring points near the Zar-3 site. Access to 3 monitoring points (labelled in red) was not possible in 2022 nor in 2023.

Groundwater level measurements were performed in five boreholes and five wells. Measurements were made with the water-level indicator cable with ca. 1 cm accuracy. Results of groundwater level are shown in Fig. 2.7-8.

Fig. 2.7-8: Results of groundwater level measurements (m) in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023.

Spring yield was monitored in two cases. The water flowing out of the spring was collected in a container – the time taken to fill the container was measured and the yield in litres per second determined. Results of spring yield are shown in Fig. 2.7-9.

Fig. 2.7-9: Spring yields (litres /sec) of monitored objects ZA008 and ZA019 measured from 2021 to 2023.

The conductivity of a groundwater is highly dependent on the concentration of dissolved salts and other chemical species that ionize in the solution. Electrical conductivity of water samples is used as an indicator of how salt-free, ion-free, or impurity-free the sample is; the purer the water, the lower the conductivity and vice versa. Conductivity measurements in water are usually reported as specific conductance, relative to the conductivity of pure water at 25 °C. An EC meter capable of providing such values was used to measure water conductivity at Zar-3 (Fig. 2.7-10).

The pH indicates the concentration of hydrogen ions in the solution. At 25 °C, solutions with a pH less than 7 are acidic, and solutions with a pH above 7 are basic. Solutions

with a pH of 7 at this temperature are neutral (e.g. pure water). The measurement results are shown in Fig. 2.7-11.

Fig. 2.7-10: Results of water electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) measurements in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023.

Fig. 2.7-11: Measured water pH (-) in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023.

The water temperature reflects the depth of its circulation; water with a shallow circulation is more reflective to changes in air temperature throughout the year and vice versa. The measurement results are shown in Fig. 2.7-12.

Fig. 2.7-12: Water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023.

The measured water temperatures reflect the effect of seasonal variations in air temperature and the depth of water circulation. Waters with deeper circulation have less difference between the temperature values measured in the warmer and colder parts of the year than waters with circulation closer to the surface.

The results of the individual measurements reflect the natural conditions in the area of interest, except for minor deviations that can be attributed to inaccuracies and errors. The water temperature and groundwater level reflect the effect of seasonal variations

(temperature) and the depth of water circulation. Water with deeper circulation has more stable temperature during different season of the year (and vice versa). The preliminary results indicate no anomalies were observed in area (nor in water temperature and level, spring yields, conductivity or pH). All data measured from 2021 to 2023 correspond to the expected natural conditions typical for wider region of the area of interest.

All the determined values were stored in the database managed by CGS. Due to the regular three-year monitoring, basic comparative values for individual parameters are available. The individual objects used for the shallow groundwater monitoring can be easily accessed and re-used in the future for possible comparative measurements. The possible impact of the CO₂ injection and storage can thus be monitored.

Hydrogeological model of groundwater flow

In order to assess potential contamination of shallow groundwater by possible CO₂ leakage, a shallow hydrogeological model of the overburden of the storage area was created in 2023 by VSB.

The results of the shallow groundwater flow model are presented in the form of groundwater level contours for individual layers in 3D (Fig. 2.7-13) and in 2D (Fig. 2.7-14, Fig. 2.7-15).

Fig. 2.7-13: Shallow groundwater level contours in model domain.

One of the objectives of the modelling study was to analyse the risk of CO₂ leakage through the monitoring well. Since the software used only allows the simulation of single phase fluid flow, leakage was simulated through H⁺ ions that would be hydrochemically generated after the release of gaseous CO₂ into groundwater. The transport was simulated as advective-dispersive since reactive transport is not expected in the case of H⁺ ions.

Transport was simulated as transient in a stationary flow field, the simulation period was 20 years. Taking into account the objective of the study, a conservative scenario was chosen: a CO₂ leaky well with a constant source of H⁺ ions of 7.94.10⁻⁶ mol/L. The initial concentration and the concentration in the precipitation were given 3.16.10⁻⁸ mol/l. Transport modelling was performed in MT3DMS and particle tracking in MODPATH. The results of transport modelling in MT3DMS are presented in Fig. 2-

Fig. 2-16: Transport modelling of H⁺ ions, simulation of 20 years of transport in steady state flow field, the length of plume in the first layer 715 m, in the fifth layer 180 m.

The solute transport modelling proved the low mobility of solutes in low permeable rock environment in the model. The only vulnerable layer is Quaternary layer where the solutes are transported towards the closest drainage base – stream in the distance of 715 m. In the flysch rock mass the transport path did not exceed 180 m from the borehole.

Fig. 2.7- shows the same results in 2D in the first layer. On the right there are results of particle tracking from the monitoring borehole. It is obvious that the impact of potential leakage is based on the modelling very local.

Fig. 2.7-17: Transport modelling results, H⁺ ions plume after 20 years (left), particle tracking in steady state flow field (right) in the first Quaternary layer (the length of plume in the first layer 715 m)

The groundwater flow and solute transport model was built and calibrated in the model domain at natural hydrological boundaries (catchment). The modelling study supports the expectation of very low permeable hydrogeological structures with low recharge. The majority of groundwater flow is located within narrow alluvial deposits and the weathered zone of the Carpathian flysch; the flow directions are consistent with the terrain.

The simulation of potential leakage from the monitoring borehole of the storage reservoir impacted only very locally the shallow zone based on the model. Thus, the potential environmental impact of leakage would be very low.

Task 7.5 – Reservoir containment monitoring

The main purpose of this Task is to prepare a reservoir containment monitoring system. The task is executed by NORCE and MND, under NORCE leadership. The advanced monitoring technology developed at NORCE (Shchipanov et al., 2019⁴) will be evaluated in this task combining results of reservoir simulations with time-lapse pressure transient analysis. During 2023, the extended analysis of dynamic data has been finished (input from Task 3.2 to Task 7.5) and the boundary conditions of the reservoir and their reflection in the real pressure transient data, available for the field, have been evaluated. The real dynamic data analysis has confirmed that the reservoir seems to be limited (no-flow boundaries) from all sides with a limited brine-saturated pore volume (aquifer) below the oil-water contact (OWC). The analysis of the boundary conditions reflected in the pressure transients interpreted provides base-line response to be used in further evaluations of deviations from the response due to potential leakage, e.g. via legacy wells in this task. The history matching of the reservoir model in WP3

⁴ Shchipanov A.A., Kollbotn L., Berenblyum R. Characterization and monitoring of reservoir flow barriers from pressure transient analysis for CO₂ injection in saline aquifers. International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control. Volume 91, December 2019, doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2019.102842.

has been finished recently in 2023. The reservoir simulation activities planned for 2023 in this task were therefore moved to 2024 and should be finished within Q1-2024. This will lead to corresponding delay with delivering the result R7.6 ‘Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring’.

Task 7.6 – Site monitoring plan

This task started in January 2023. Conclusions from all the WP7 tasks are being collected together with experience from other CO₂ storage projects worldwide. The initial draft version of result **V5 Site monitoring plan** (type O) was written in 2023.

Deviations and changes

Some deviations from the work plan were reported in WP7, however, none of them will have negative influence on achievement of WP objectives or execution of other Work Packages. Delay is reported in T7.5 (R7.6).

Task 7.5: The work is behind schedule due to the Injection Step-Rate issues. The Injection Step-Rate test was postponed several times due to the technical reasons (e.g. waiting for drilling rig; postponed delivery of tubing material) and was finally performed in December 2023, so the planned input to the **V5 Site monitoring plan** (T7.6) will be provided in due time. The result **R7.6 Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring** (deadline 3/2023) is postponed to 03/2024.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Main results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
TO01000 112-V3	Set of thematic maps of the CO ₂ Zar-3 storage site – joint result of WP1, WP6, WP7 and WP8	12/2023

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R7.8	Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO ₂ plume monitoring	12/2022 Delivered 11/2023
R7.3	Data set and Technical Report on atmogeochemical monitoring results	11/2023
R7.5	Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring (Task 7.4)	11/2023
R7.6	Data set and report with results of reservoir containment monitoring (Task 7.5)	03/2023 Postponed to 03/2024

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

2.8 WORK PACKAGE 8 – Scenarios of future development

Summary

The main objective of the Work Package 8 (WP8) is to prepare future site development plans, and design surface and subsurface facilities for the selected pilot site. The work was ongoing according to the plan to finalize both the facility design and CCUS value chain scenarios. NORCE coordinated the work as WP leader; CGS and MND provided contributions to Tasks 8.1 and 8.3. The activities in Task 8.2 were carried out by NORCE and MND.

Task 8.1 – Value chain analysis for CO₂ supply, transport, EOR and storage

Value chain analysis continued with important addition of the scenario in which MND is injecting its own emissions. One of the largest issues is that Zar-3 field is a relatively small one with an estimated storage capacity around 1 Mt and it needs a fitting source of CO₂. Another complication is transport. While truck delivery was found feasible for the pilot, the traffic capacity may limit a large-scale deployment. Another transport option, the pipeline, may deliver sufficient capacity, while being too costly for a stand-alone project. While there are several medium to large scale emitters in the area at a given time, building a whole value chain with several fields in the storage complex appears to be too ambitious.

Instead, two alternative opportunities topping up small own emissions are being evaluated:

- Blue hydrogen production
- Direct air capture on site

and will be reported in the final reporting period.

Task 8.2 – Design of facilities for pilot implementation

The work on designing the facilities continued. While majority of the findings from the previous period stayed the same, the well was changed from ZA3 to ZA7. This should allow for faster and simpler implementation as the well is perforated into the water zone with fitting completion. The update connection scheme is shown in Fig. 2.8-1.

Fig. 2.8-1: Connection scheme of facility Zar-3

A cryogenic scenario with larger trucks was selected as a most plausible option. MND is also looking at possibility of storing its own emissions. This scenario will also be evaluated.

Task 8.3 – Scenarios for future site development

During the third reporting period the work on potential scenarios continued and scenarios were evaluated. The effect of pilot-scale CO₂ injection providing pressure support for ongoing field operation as well as beginning full-scale storage operation during contra post gas blowdown from the reservoir were estimated. The results have shown that the demonstration scale pilot project may be safely conducted in parallel to the tail-end production. Two options were assessed for the full-scale storage: 1) during production and 2) after production end. The first option may provide pressure support, prevent excessive pressure decline and allow for fast-tracking CO₂ injection. The second option, storage after production, may allow for a somewhat higher gas recovery (due to solution gas release), avoiding of CO₂ back production and production facilities upgrades, and, overall, is more conventional from the legal and resource management points of view.

Remaining scenarios are:

- Alternative 2: Blue hydrogen from Zar-3 gas
- Alternative 3 Classical EOR (Enhanced Oil Recovery)
- Alternative 4: Direct air capture.

The activity of WP8 will be finalized and delivered in accordance with plan in and budget in 2024.

Deviations and changes

The work in WP8 was carried out according to the work plan.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

No results were planned for this reporting period.

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

2.9 WORK PACKAGE 9 – Communication and dissemination

Summary

The main aim of project communication and dissemination activities is to create awareness of the existence of the project, disseminate project results to identified target groups to achieve the planned impact, raise general awareness of CCS as an important climate change mitigation technology and highlight the bilateral Czech-Norwegian cooperation based on project funding from Norway Grants.

The work in WP9 was carried out according to the work plan. CGS led the WP9 activities as WP leader, all Project Partners contributed to the work.

Task 9.1 – Project events

Two project meetings took place in Hodonín (June 2023) and Ostrava (November 2023) and one Czech Norwegian workshop in Trondheim in June 2023 (see result R9.12).

Task 9.2 – Website

The project website at the address “<https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz>” was maintained in both Czech and English versions and updated during the whole year 2023 by adding fresh project news, promotion material, presentations from conferences and links to publications.

Fig. 2.9-1: CO₂-SPICER project website (updated English version) – subpage Downloads with a few examples of project communication outcomes.

Task 9.3 – Presentations and publications

In 2023, the project results were presented at four international conferences – 11 oral and poster presentations.

- *TCCS-12 – 12th Trondheim Conference on CO₂ Capture, Transport and Storage. June, 2023, Trondheim, Norway (Fig. 2.9-2):*

1. Preparing for CO₂ pilot in the Czech Republic. TCCS-12. Authors: R. Berenblyum, V. Hladík†, J. Franců, M. Pereszlényi, E. Hudečková, V. Kolejka, V. Opletal, M. Pagáč, A. Shchipanov, A. Nermoen, E. Ford, P. Jirman, M. Klempa, P. Kolář.

2. Seasonal climatic constraints of soil-gas baseline monitoring at the Zar-3 pilot CO₂ storage site, Czechia. TCCS-12. Authors: P. Jirman, J. Franců, V. Hladík †, P. Pařízek.

3. Risk and reliability analyses: Examples of applications focusing on P&A and CO₂ storage. TCCS-12. Author: Eric Patrick Ford (NORCE).

4. Rock strengths and Earth stresses – assessing safe operation envelope during CO₂ storage in a mature oil and gas field. TCCS-12. Authors: A. Nermoen, M. M. Porzer, J. Sa Sancer, A. Shchipanov, V. Hladik, M. Klempa.

5. Decision making under uncertainty case study from a Czech Republic CO₂ storage. TCCS-12. Authors: E. P. Ford, A. Nermoen , H. P. Lohne, A. Shchipanov, R. Berenblyum , M. M. Porzer.

6. Single-cell reservoir model for CO₂ storage planning. TCCS-12. Authors: A. Khrulenko and R. Berenblyum (NORCE).

Fig. 2.9-2: TCCS-12 – 12th Trondheim Conference on CO₂ Capture, Transport and Storage. June, 2023, Trondheim, Norway.

- *IMOG – 31st International Meeting on Organic Geochemistry (IMOG), 10-15 September, 2023, Montpellier, France (Fig. 2.9-3):*

7. Seal efficiency evaluation in the Zar-3 pilot CCS using biomarkers, mudlogs and isotopes in reservoir and caprocks, SE Czechia. IMOG. Authors: J. Franců, D. Ocásková, M. Pereszlényi, P. Pařízek, P. Jirman, R. Prochác, V. Hladík†

8. Soil gas monitoring experience from above underground gas storage and a pilot CO₂ storage, Czechia. IMOG, Authors: J. Franců, P. Jirman, V. Hladík†

Fig. 2.9-3: 31st International Meeting on Organic Geochemistry (IMOG), 10-15 September, 2023, Montpellier, France

- *GeoNet – 16th CO₂ GeoNet Open Forum, 2-5 October, 2023, San Servolo, Venice, Italy:*

9. Preparatory work for CO₂ pilot injection into naturally fractured carbonate reservoir in the Czech Republic. GeoNet, Authors: M. Pagac, P. Jirman, M. Libcinska, R. Berenblyum, A. Nermoen, E. P. Ford.

10. Carbon storage in dolomite reservoir: rock-fluid-CO₂ interactions. GeoNet, Authors: J. Vácha, Š. Káňa, L. Jurenka, J. Franců, M. Klempa.

- *ICMRI 2023 – International Conference On Multidisciplinary Research And Innovation. 9-10.April, 2023, Istanbul, Turkey:*

11. Study of mechanical-elastic parameters of reservoir rocks with respect to the purpose of permanent CO₂ storage. ICMRI 2023. Authors: A. Lacman, M. Křístek, P. Žilová and M. Klempa.

In addition to the presentations, the related papers or paper abstracts were published in conference proceedings of these events. All project presentations and publications are available on project website at <https://co2-spicer.geology.cz/en/downloads>.

An important part of communication activities was the liaison with other projects funded by EEA/Norway Grants. Within the continued partnership with the CCS4CEE project (Building momentum for the long-term CCS deployment in the CEE region), funded from the Fund for Regional Cooperation of EEA/Norway Grants, CO₂-SPICER coordinator provided consultations and input to the National CCS roadmap for the Czech Republic that was prepared by EUROPEUM – the Czech partner of the CCS4CEE project. A presentation was made on 'Potential of the Czech Republic for

geological storage of CO₂ at the National CCS seminar organised by EUROPEUM on the occasion of launching the Czech CCS roadmap in Prague.

Communication activities addressing industrial stakeholders included a series of bilateral consultations, both face-to-face and online, that were devoted to possibilities of utilisation of CCS technology as a solution for reduction of CO₂ emissions from industrial facilities, sharing information about the CO₂-SPICER project, discussions on future utilisation of its results and possible participation of the industry representatives in CO₂-SPICER **End-User Group**. The consulted companies included Českomoravský Cement a.s., ČD Cargo, SMOLO a.s. and Lafarge Cement Čížkovice. Consultations were also provided to the Ministry of Industry and Trade and the Ministry of Environmental of the Czech Republic. A report “Introduction to CO₂ Storage in geological formations in the Czech Republic and neighbouring countries: Implications for the lime production of Vápenka Čertovy Schody, a.s., Lhoist Central Europe, Tmář u Berouna” was prepared by J. Franců and M. Pereszlényi for the Association of Lime Producers in the CR in September 2023.

University students form an important target group of project communication. In 2021, VŠB – the project partner attracted four students of the university (VŠB – Technical University of Ostrava) to participate in the research dealt with in the CO₂-SPICER and prepare their final theses. In 2023, works on two thesis were still in progress:

- Josef Čožík (2023 in progress): Utilization of Dipole Electromagnetic Profiling for CO₂ Monitoring Optimalization at the Žarošice Site. Bachelor thesis, M. Klempa - tutor.
- Adam Lacman (2023 in progress): Research into the Influence of Carbon Dioxide on the Reservoir Properties of the Žarošice Oil Field. PhD thesis, M. Klempa - tutor.

CO₂-SPICER project **implementation** continued to attract **media** interest in 2023. Project Partners CGS provided interested journalists with interviews and/or written information. Both thematically profiled media and those with nationwide coverage (e.g. Seznam Zprávy or CZECHCRUNCH) showed interested in the project and the CCS technology in general. Examples of articles are shown in Fig. 2.9-4 to 2.9-7.

Vysavač CO₂ jako záchrana klimatu

Geoinženýrské technologie

Cílem geoinženýrství je záměrně ovlivnit klimatický systém Země, aby se zastavilo globální oteplování. V současné době je v centru pozornosti zejména jedna metoda: odstraňování CO₂ ze vzduchu.

MONIQUE OPETZ

O brovské vysavače CO₂ a filtry oxidu uhličitého, které odfiltrují z atmosféry plyn, jenž poškozuje klima – ziti to jako sci-fi, ale už je to realita. Například v Kanadě, Norsku nebo na Islandu v geotermální elektrárně Hellisheiði, kde je od roku 2021 umístěno největší komerční zařízení na zachycování a podzemní ukládání CO₂. Filtrní zařízení CO₂ Orca od společnosti Climeworks se skládá ze čtyř obrovských kovových boxů, které připomínají kontejnery s na sebe naskládanými

ZELENÉ ČIPY
Nové technologie pro klimaticky neutrální budoucnost
Výzkumné instituce, firmy, veřejné iniciativy a vynálezci se snaží zastavit změnu klimatu. Všechny mají jedno společné: jsou pokročilými nejmodernějšími technologiemi. ČHP vám je v této rubrice představuje.

lamelami. Jsou vybaveny říditelnými ventilátory a filtry, které nasávají oxid uhličitý ze vzduchu, shromažďují ho a následně izolují. Tímto způsobem by mělo zařízení Orca z atmosféry odstranit 4 000 tun CO₂ ročně. Pro srovnání, celosvětové emise oxidu uhličitého v roce 2021 činily 32,2 miliardy tun. Podle studie Mezinárodní energetické agentury (IEA) je v současné době na světě sedm komerčních zařízení, která zachycují a ukládají deset miliónů tun CO₂ ročně. Brzy přibude na Islandu

Fig. 2.9-4: “Vacuum cleaner of CO₂ from the air as a climate saver”.

První firma za peníze pochytila CO2 ze vzduchu a uložila pod zem. Nadějná metoda může masově uspět

Zařízené švýcarské firmy ročně pochyti asi čtyři tisíce tun CO2, což je málo. Konkurent ale buduje zařízení, které zvládne až půl milionu tun.

ELIŠKA NOVÁ

Sdílet f t in

První komerční zařízení na zachytávání CO₂ je na Islandu

Mezi jejími zákazníky patří třeba Microsoft, který společnosti Climeworks už dříve předem zaplatil, aby se vypořádala s jeho uhlíkovou stopou. Teď to konečně zvládla. Švýcarská firma oznámila, že se jí podařilo zachytit oxid uhlíčitý z atmosféry a uložit ho pod zem. A použila na to speciální technologii, která sice funguje už asi sedmdesát let, ale až teď byla úspěšně využita pro sběr CO₂, respektive ochranu klimatu.

„Příkladem využití mohou být ponorky nebo kosmické lodě, kde je potřeba obsah CO₂ ve vzduchu systematicky snižovat,“ říká na úvod Vít Hladík z České geologické služby. „Počátky klimaticky orientovaných aktivit lze datovat někdy do roku 1999, kdy profesor Lackner z Arizony přišel s konceptem takzvaných umělých stromů. Od té doby se technologie intenzivně vyvíjí, jejím širšímu uplatnění zatím brání hlavně vysoké náklady,“ doplňuje.

Až dosud se zachycený oxid uhlíčitý používal například pro výrobu syntetických paliv nebo zásobování skleníků. Druhou stránkou nového konceptu je uložení

NEJČTENĚJŠÍ ČLÁNKY

Týden Měsíc

- 1 Stačí jeden akciový index a do konce života nemusíte nic odlat. Říká autor Rozbitého prasadka
- 2 Proč ve dne, když v noci je to větší akce. Lindsey Vonn jako první žena sjela nejročnější trat světa
- 3 Když se ostatní probouzí, mám půlku práce hotovou. Říká právníčka, která platí i ve vojách

SLEDUJTE NÁS

f 60k t 22.8k
in 37.1k

NEPŘEHLEDNĚTE

Fig. 2.9-5: Sorption of CO₂ from the air in Iceland.

Seršal o plastech XXXXII.: CO₂ jako surovina
Dě 8. 2023 | Autor: Pavlína Votavová

Podle Mezinárodní energetické agentury (IEA) je světový chemický průmysl třetím v pořadí průmyslových odvětví z hlediska množství přímých emisí CO₂ – za výrobu kovu a cementu.

Začátkem tohoto roku publikovala Evropská komise publikaci Transition Pathway for the Chemical Industry, ve které představuje základy jeho zelené a digitální transformace. Konstatuje, že chemický průmysl hraje strategickou roli v evropské ekonomice v ležici od výroby chemikálií, jejich modifikací a produkci žitných výrobků pro různé aplikace v sektoru.

Z hlediska finančního obrátu se evropský chemický průmysl řadí na druhé místo mezi světovými regiony za domovinou Čínu. V roce 2020 se v Evropě jednalo o obrát 499 miliard eur a podle na evropském obrátu 14,6 %, když ještě v roce 2000 Evropa vykazala výši podíl 24,9 %. Další pokles podle na 10,5 %, se prognózuje do roku 2030. Z hlediska nečistotových emisí skleníkových plynů se chemický průmysl EU 27 podílí 9 % na celoevropských emisích.

Evropská asociace CEPIC ještě nezveřejnila výsledky za rok 2021, kdy tento sektor trpěl pandemií, výšší cenami energií a surovin, logistickými problémy a nižšími odbytem. Experti však odhadují srovnatelné hodnoty jako v roce 2020.

Rok 2022 by znamenala výzvu na Ukrajině, což se má projevit v hodnotách za 11 měsíců roku 2022 – ústřední ve farmaceutickém průmyslu o 23,6 %, ve strojírenství o 49 %, v automobilovém průmyslu o 4,4 %, opoziční státnímu obchodu roku 2021. Největší pokles – o 5,1 % – zaznamenala evropský chemický průmysl, který zaměstná 1,2 milionu pracovníků, následovaná výrobou kovu a nábí výrobou o 3,6 %.

Samotná výroba plastů a kaučuků zaznamenala vloni v EU 27 pokles o 1,2 %. Za Achillovu patu evropského chemického průmyslu je považována výroba cenné křemíkové suroviny – etylenu z parních křádků, která byla např. v prvním pololetí 2021 téměř dvojnásobně proti cenám v Severní Americe a 3,3. krát vyšší než ve střední Asii.

„Čističky vzduchu“ změny klimatu zázračně nevyřeší, jsou součástí skládačky
Zprávy > Domácí > Život v Česku > „Čističky vzduchu“ změny klimatu zázračně nevyřeší, jsou so...

JAN KORDOVSKÝ

Jedna z prvních továren, které při těžbě plynu zároveň zachytávají CO₂ a ukládají ho zpět pod zem.

5. 11. 19:43

Kromě snižování našich emisí existují i průmyslové pokusy o zachytávání CO₂ a jeho následné ukládky. Juraj Franců z České geologické služby v rozhovoru popisuje, jak celý proces funguje a jaká má úskalí.

Fig. 2.9-6: Samples of articles on CCS in the Czech media.

Apple Podcasts Preview

29 min

PLAY ▶

Proč nestačí "čistit" vzduch? Jak funguje zachytávání CO₂

Stopáž

Technology

Oxid uhličitý je jedním z nejproblematičtějších skleníkových plynů. Od průmyslové revoluce ho uvolňujeme až padesát milionkrát rychleji, než původně vznikal. Kromě snižování našich emisí existují i průmyslové pokusy o zachytávání CO₂ a jeho následné ukládání. Juraj Franců z České geologické služby v rozhovoru dnešní Stopáže popisuje, jak celý proces funguje, a jaká má úskalí.

Stopáž je podcast pro ty, které zajímá, kam se za uplynulý týden posunul svět, ale nemají čas neustále sledovat Twitter. Přehled těch nejzajímavějších zpráv připravuje Jan Kordovský (@korda). Vychází každý pátek v poledne.

Další podcasty, ale taky články, komentáře a videa najdete na Seznamáckém serveru Podcasty.cz.

Poslouchejte nás na webu nebo ve vaší oblíbené podcastové aplikaci.

Vaše názory, návrhy, otázky, stížnosti nebo pochvaly nám můžete posílat na adresu jan.kordovsky@sz.cz.

Stopáž vzniká v zázemí Seznam.cz.

Fig. 2.9-7: Apple Podcast on Seznam.cz – Geological CO₂ storage, interview by Juraj Francu, CGS (in Czech).

An overview of project media coverage is available on project website (Czech version) at <https://CO2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/zajimave-odkazy>.

Task 9.10 – Article in popular and science journal

An article about the CO₂-SPICER project is published in the online version of the VSB-TUO Akademik University Newsletter (<https://www.vsb.cz/magazin/cs/detail-novinky?reportId=46507>). Paper is under preparation about CCS and CO₂-SPICER project to be published in the science popularization journal Vesmír.

An article was published: **Study of Mechanical-Elastic Parameters of Reservoir Rocks with Respect to the Purpose of Permanent CO₂ Storage**. Research paper in Metallurgical and Materials Engineering (printed ISSN 2217-8961, online ISSN 2812-9105). Authors: Lacman, A., Křístek, M., Karol, P., Klempa, M. (2023).

Task 9.11 – Project newsletter

The Czech Geological Survey has published a second issue of the newsletter of the CO₂-SPICER project, which provides updates on recent activities and primarily presents the partial results of the project. The document is available in print form and on-line form on the webpage: <https://co2-spicer.geology.cz/cs/ke-stazeni>.

Fig. 2.9-8: Samples of newsletter pages.

Deviations and changes

The work in WP9 was carried out according to the work plan.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		Date of submission
No.	Result title	
R9.10	Article in popular science journal	10/2023
R9.11	Project newsletter	2/2023

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

2.10 WORK PACKAGE 10 – Project management and reporting

Summary

The main goal of Work Package 10 is to ensure that the project runs as smoothly as possible. The project management structure, as well as the duties at different management levels were defined with a great attention to detail already during the project preparation stage, and have been incorporated in the Project Contract and the Partnership Agreement. Work Package 10 covers all project management, organisation and other related tasks; in 2023 the work progressed according to the plan. Work Package 10 was led by CGS (WP leader), with participation of all partners.

Task 10.1 – Project and Work Package Coordination and Management

This Task includes the management of the project and its key activities by the Project coordinator and leaders of the 10 defined Work Packages (WP1-WP10). In addition, it also covers the work of the project's three governing bodies – the General Assembly, Management Board and End-User Group.

The General Assembly is the highest decision-making body of the project. All partners involved in the project have one representative in the General Assembly, their respective voting powers (number of votes) corresponding to the scope of the partner's involvement in the project (in person-months of work). The third meeting of the General Assembly was held in the form of a personal meeting as a part of the project meeting in Hodonín on 14 June 2023. Minutes of the meeting are enclosed as a separate attachment to the Interim report, together with the Management Board meetings minutes.

The Management Board supports the Project coordinator in operative project management and housekeeping duties. It consists of the Project coordinator (Principal investigator) and the Work Packages leaders. In addition, the representatives of Project Partners also participate in Management Board meetings to ensure smooth flow of information across the whole project team. In 2023, Management Board meetings were held regularly once a month (usually on every second Thursday of each month except July due to holidays) mainly in the form of teleconferences. The June Management Board meeting was organised as a physical meeting, as part of the project meeting in Hodonín and similarly during the November project meeting in Ostrava. Minutes of the 11 meetings (in the order 27 to 37) are presented in a separate attachment to the Interim report.

The formation of the End-User Group is in process, negotiations with candidates have been carried on in 2023. The candidates include industrial companies, such as Českomoravský cement, Heidelberg group, Lhoist Central Europe, Tmář u Berouna (Vápenka Čertovy schody), Liberty Ostrava and others. The End-User Group meeting will be held simultaneously with the Final project conference in Prague in March 2024.

Task 10.1 also covers the preparation and organisation of project meetings. During the 3rd project period, two project meetings were organized, both in-person, with the possibility of online connection for those participants who could not participate face-to-face. The 5th project meeting was held in Hodonín at MND headquarters on 13th June 2023 and the 6th meeting took place at the VSB TUO in Ostrava on 21st November 2023. Minutes of the meetings are provided in a separate attachment to the Interim

report, together with the Management Board meetings minutes. In both cases, several WPs or topic-related joint workshops (modelling, future scenarios, geochemistry and geomechanics, risk assessment) were affiliated with the project meetings as needed.

Task 10.1 work is organised and implemented by CGS; the participation of other Project Partners corresponds to their involvement in the management of the different Work Packages. All partners were involved in the organization of the project meetings.

Task 10.2 – Project Administration, Liaison with Programme Operator, Reporting

The purpose of this Task is to provide administrative support to the project management team, both during routine, day-to-day operations and in the preparation of interim reports and the final report. The Task covers also the practicalities of ongoing cooperation with the Programme Operator (TA ČR) and the preparation of projects reports by the Project coordinator, WP leaders and Project Partners.

In January 2023, the 2nd interim report for period 01-12/2022 was submitted. Compilation of the report profited a lot from the information provided at a special TA ČR webinar in 2021 and from the experience from the previous interim report.

No Project monitoring (on-site) audit organised by TACR took place in 2023, all project uncertainties were solved by means of questions and tickets at the helpdesk in ISTA/SISTA system or by telephone consultations with the responsible staff.

An important part of the project administration efforts are the **public procurement procedures** to accommodate the planned sub-contracts, purchases of materials and services needed by the project in full compliance with applicable regulations (in particular applicable public procurement legislation and internal procurement policies of all partners).

A public tender procedure with the aim to award a sub-contract “Feasibility study on the applicability of seismic survey for monitoring of the CO₂ plume at Zar-3” for WP7 was organised in the second half of 2022 and due to the necessity to prepare all needed documents in both Czech and English versions, the public tender was launched only on October 2022 and was finalized in November 2022. The agreement with the “winner” of the **public tender**, Mr Roman Pevzner, sole trader, Australia, was signed in May 2023. The final study was submitted to CGS as contractor in October 2023 – see result R7.8.

The second public tendering “Well integrity logging” (WP6) was open in May 2023 without any response. The repeated call of July 2023 also resulted in “no reply”. In autumn 2023, the term of well ZA7 availability for well integrity logging measurement was unclear. In late October 2023 the operator of ZA7 well (MND) informed CGS that the well will be available in 2 weeks, i.e. in middle November 2023. After two unsuccessful calls of public tendering, CGS asked directly the company KaC (this is the only one company in the Czech Republic with adequate equipment and experience) for well integrity logging measurement. The Director of the CGS, as the responsible representative, decided to grant an exception from his authority and to authorise a direct procurement; the third call of the tender would not be able to meet the deadline given by the MND. Well integrity logging on ZA7 well was successfully finalized on November 12, 2023 – see result R6.4.

Other purchases of material and services were carried out using the usual procedures of Project Partners.

Task 10.2 work is managed by CGS, benefitting from support of an administrative team headed by Project administrator. All Project Partners contribute to the reporting activities.

Task 10.3 – Economic and financial management of the project

Actual project costs of the second monitoring period 01-12/2022 were reported in the 2nd Interim Report submitted in January 2023, including relevant documents and other materials. During 2023, all project costs and expenses have been tracked on ongoing basis and continuously compared with approved budget. In December 2023, preparation for financial reporting within the 3rd Interim Report was started. Justification of the costs incurred in the reporting period are provided in chapter 6.

Task 10.3 is carried out by the Project administrator at CGS, supported by the CGS Accounting Department. All partners appointed a person responsible for regular transfers of economic data to Project administrator and provided the required input.

Deviations and changes

The only deviation from the plan is the delay with establishment of the End-User Group, but negotiations with potential Group participants (mostly industrial companies) continued during 2023 with promising results. The End-User Group meeting will be held simultaneously with the Final project conference in Prague in 2024.

WP results achieved in the reporting period

Other results		
No.	Result title	Date of submission
R10.2	Project interim reports in ISTA	1/2023

Milestones

No milestones are defined for this Work Package.

3 INVOLVEMENT OF CONSORTIUM MEMBERS IN PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION

All consortium members (Project Partners) have been actively involved in project execution in 2023. Their roles and responsibilities are clearly defined in the Partnership Agreement, and, in particular, in its Attachment 6 “Project content & Detailed description of Work Packages”. This document specifies the work and role of each partner in every Work Package and Task in detail.

In the 3rd reporting period, all Project Partners contributed to project implementation according to the plan. No major issues related to cooperation within the consortium incurred, and the minor ones were successfully solved on the ground of the Management Board. The contributions of individual Project Partners to implementation of the work plan in individual Work Packages and Tasks are described in detail in Chapter 2.

4 JUSTIFICATION FOR CHANGES IN THE PROJECT TEAM

The total actual workload reported in the third period of CO₂-SPICER is 9.7 person-years (FTE), which corresponds to 116.6 % of the plan. This figure corresponds well to the reported progress of the project and the slight deviations reported.

Key persons

The project coordinator of the CO₂-SPICER project, Mr. Vít Hladík passed away on 3rd Feb. 2023. Juraj Franců was proposed as the new project coordinator and approved by the General Assembly members and the director of CGS in Feb. 2023. There were no other changes in the composition of the key persons’ team in 2023.

Other persons

The CO₂-SPICER project team consists of more than 70 researchers and technicians working in five institutions. It was therefore very difficult to exactly plan the working capacity of each person / position in each year, and in many cases only estimations had to be made for the planning table. Therefore, there are slight deviations in actual working capacities in comparison to the plan of majority of the team members. The actual figures reflect the real needs of the project’s 10 Work Packages documented in the time sheets filled in by each team member on monthly basis. These detailed deviations per person and position are not described in the report for proportional reasons.

Action Plan on improving the gender balance and early-stage career researchers’ involvement.

The Action Plan was submitted by the Project Consortium at the beginning of the project as a condition set by TA ČR for Project Contract signature. The implementation of the planned actions should have been reported annually to TACR within the annual project reports.

The current status of implementation of the Plan is as follows:

1. *Consortium will include 10 female researchers and technicians in the project team from the beginning of the project and increase this number to 15 in the 3rd project year at the latest.*

Implementation: 15 female researchers and technicians were involved in project implementation in the 3rd reporting period (8 at CGS, 4 at VSB, 2 at MND and 1 at GFU).

2. *Consortium will engage at least three early-career researchers in the solution of the project during the first project year and increase this number to five in the 3rd project year.*

Implementation: One early-career researcher continued in engagement in project solution in the 3rd reporting period – Adam Lacman (PhD student at VSB), while in 2022 another PhD student at VSB (Matěj Křístek) stopped his work on the project. In CGS four early-career researchers have been involved in the project in 2023: Petr Jirman – PostDoc, Tomáš Vlček – postdoc, Jakub Vácha – graduate student and Lucie Stejskalová – graduate student. The total number of early-career researchers participating in project solution in the 3rd reporting period is five.

3. *Project Promoter CGS will appoint a young, early-career researcher as co-leader of Work Package 7 ‘Monitoring’, starting from the beginning of the project, with the prospect of taking over the full WP leadership after gaining sufficient experience and skills, in the concrete from the start of the 3rd project year at the latest.*

Implementation: The PostDoc, Petr Jirman was appointed as WP7 co-leader from the beginning of the project and took fully over the WP leadership in full from summer 2021.

4. *Project Partner MND will engage a female researcher to act as co-leader of Work Package 2 ‘3D geological model of the storage complex’ from the beginning of the project.*

Implementation: Lenka Klímová has been acting as WP2 co-leader since the beginning of the project.

5. *Project Partner NORCE will use the established collaboration with the University of Stavanger (UiS) on supervising MSc. thesis to suggest and supervise MSc. topics related to CO₂-SPICER activities for the students at UiS. Results of the theses will be publicly available and will contribute to increasing involvement of early career researchers and dissemination of the project results.*

Implementation: Project Partner NORCE collaborates not only with the University of Stavanger (UiS) but also with the Sapienza University of Rome (SUoR). Mr. Hassan Khaled, student of SUoR, defended MSc. thesis “Well testing before CO₂ Injection” under the supervision of a Norwegian project participant, Mr. Anton Shchipanov. <https://co2geonet.com/news-and-events/news/final-defence-ceremony-of-the-master-2023/>

In addition to the original plan, Project Partner VŠB has already launched a similar action at their university in 2021-2023. Based on this, one PhD. thesis is close to the defence (2024): Adam Lacman “Research into the Influence of Carbon Dioxide on the Reservoir Properties of the Žarošice Oil Field”.

In general, the status of implementation of the Action Plan in the 3rd project period is considered satisfactory, good results are reported for all the five planned actions.

5 MANAGEMENT BOARD ACTIVITIES

The Management Board (corresponds to the project steering committee) is the Project's governing body responsible for operative project management. It consists of the Project coordinator (Principal investigator), all Work Package leaders and consortium partners' representatives. In the third project period, Management Board meetings were held online on monthly basis, usually on the second Thursday of each month, only in July there was no meeting due to the holidays. In June, the Management Board meeting was organised face-to-face in Hodonín and the November meeting in Ostrava was also held in person.

During Management Board meetings, the progress of work in all Work Packages and other issues related to project implantation were regularly checked and discussed. Management Board was also used as a platform for definition of cooperation actions and individual responsibilities, discussion of data hand-over, sharing of information among partners, as well as for checking the progress of actions in respect to previous meetings.

Minutes of the 11 Management Board meetings held in 2023 were uploaded to "Documents and attachments" of the 3rd interim report in the ISTA system.

6 JUSTIFICATION OF THE ACTUAL COSTS INCURRED DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD

The reported CO₂-SPICER project costs of the third reporting period are 15,556,451 CZK, which corresponds to 123.9 % of the plan. The cumulative spending since the start of the project (1/11/2020) is 61,653,493, which equals to 98 % of the plan. This means that the underspending of the first and the second reporting period (87 % of the planned costs) has been partly made up.

The main part of the incurred costs belongs to the category of personnel costs (15,556,451 CZK) that correspond to the extensive reported workload of the project team - 9.7 person-years (FTE). From the beginning of the project, 32.06 person-years have been spent on the implementation of the project, which slightly exceeded the plan (105 % of the planned capacities were consumed).

Budget consumption and main project costs incurred by individual partners in 2023 are described below:

Project Promoter – CGS

Total costs incurred by CGS in the third reporting period were 8,507,783 CZK, which corresponds to 116 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 5,488,787 CZK correspond to 6.07 person-years (FTE). The reasons are the overall 10% increase in salaries at CGS since September 2022 based on a government decision. Planned subcontracting costs (in total 1,261K CZK) were partly moved to the direct employment of the relevant expert (2022) and spent (885K CZK) on two sub-contracts in frame of WP7 (Feasibility study) and WP6 (Well integrity logging) in 2023.

Approximately 82 % of planned other direct costs were spent (610K CZK). Cost savings were used to compensate for the higher personnel costs. Main cost items in this category are:

- Inland travel costs (29K CZK), mainly to the Zar-3 site for field monitoring, and to project meetings in Hodonín and Ostrava;
- Conference fees and international travel costs (277K CZK) related to presentation of the project and its results at two international conferences;
- Spare parts for instruments and consumables in WP5 (101K CZK);
- Spare parts for monitoring instruments, consumables for field work, batteries, chemicals, etc. in WP7 (125K CZK);
- Services – sample analysis, rent of gas tanks etc. in WP5 and WP7 (60K CZK);
- Sub-contracts – WP7 Feasibility study (400K CZK), WP6 Well integrity logging (488K CZK).

Project Partner MND

Total costs incurred by MND in the reporting period were 4,692,056 CZK, which corresponds to 121 % of the plan. This partly compensates for a significant underspending by MND in 2021. Personnel costs of 3,194,876 CZK were consumed more or less in accordance with the plan, corresponding to 1.67 person-years (FTE).

The main cost item in the category other direct costs is:

- SW maintenance costs (559K CZK)

Other direct costs spending in the reporting period is higher than planned; the reason is the improper planning of MND personnel and SW maintenance costs in the original budget that has been corrected in the cost statement. The SW maintenance costs were calculated according to the percentage of the use of particular SW modules for the project activities.

Project Partner NORCE

Total costs incurred by NORCE in the second reporting period were 5,924,950 CZK, which corresponds to 158 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 5,788,992 CZK, corresponding to 0.79 person-years (FTE) were consumed, which is 125.4 % of the planned amount. The main reason for this overrun is mainly due to underspending in the first reporting period, where some activities were moved from the first period to subsequent years.

Other direct costs was also higher at 136K CZK compared to 76K CZK planned due to project activity, increased travel costs.

The main cost items in the category other direct are:

- Travel costs to project meeting in Hodonin from Stavanger and Bergen (83k CZK)
- Participation in TCCS conference in Trondheim in June (46k CZK)

Overall budget consumption in the project so far is 18,611,455 CZK personnel costs (94% of planned budget) with 389 326 CZK travel budget (127% of planned budget).

It is expected that all the task would be completed within overall budget in 2024.

Project Partner VSB

Total costs incurred by VSB in the third reporting period were 1,203,905 CZK, which corresponds to 100 % of the plan. Personnel costs of 696,168 CZK, corresponding to 0.69 person-years (FTE).

Other direct costs consumption (266,971 CZK) was consistent with the plan. Main cost items in this category are:

- Travel costs (15K CZK), mostly to project meeting in Hodonín and also to the MND and to Brno for consultation;
- Machine calibration, service maintenance in WP5 – porosimeter and permeameter device, AAS and oven (126K CZK);
- Consumables - mainly laboratory material for tests and experiments in WP4 and WP5, diamond core barrels and tenzometres for WP4 and WP5, materials necessary for laboratory works and rental of pressure cylinders. (67K CZK).

Project Partner GFU

Total costs incurred by GFU in the second reporting period were 479,067 CZK, which corresponds to 97 % of the updated (2022) budget. Personnel costs of 387,628 CZK, corresponding to 0.49 person-years (FTE), were higher (108 %) than update. The original distribution of GFU project budget was updated to accommodate the significant prolongation of on-site seismic monitoring in 2023. The unspent parts of the budget from 2021 and 2022 were transferred to 2023-2024 to cover the costs related to the prolonged duration of the field operations and data processing.

Other direct costs consumption (12K CZK) was lower than the plan. Main cost items in this category are:

- Inland travel costs (12K CZK) to Zar-3 site for field work and project meetings in Hodonín and Ostrava.

7 OBSTACLES DURING THE REPORTING PERIOD

The fact that the project coordinator passed away in Feb. 2023 presented an obstacle in continuation of the project. Designation of the new coordinator, J. Franců, his close cooperation with the deputy project coordinator, V. Kolečka and project administrator, E. Hudečková and support by all the partners in the project made it possible, that the works on all WPs continued smoothly.

Inaccessibility of the core repository due to tornado in 2021 and reconstruction works in 2022 caused problems with gathering of supplemental core samples and a delay in analyses and experiments in WP4 and WP5. The situation improved very much in late 2022, when MND partner provided caprock and reference core samples from the adjacent wells. Additional 121 samples of drilling cuttings had exceptionally high value as they represent a complete geological profile of the ZA3 borehole in the centre of the pilot storage site. All the analytical and experimental works on the provided samples were carried out in 2023 with a minor extension to January 2024.

The injection step-rate test planned by MND in Task 3.2 for June 2022 was delayed to 2023 due to technical issues in the injection well and to unavailability of both the maintenance rig and spare fibreglass tubing. This caused delays in some parts of WP3

and WP7. The step-rate test was finally carried out on the 19th of December, 2023. Seismic stations were deployed in the field to monitor whether water injection caused any seismic events. Several injection periods, at different injection rates, were applied. No pressure increase was observed at the wellhead. It means, that there is no reservoir rock resistance to water storage. Observed data will be analysed in 2024.

Partial delay occurred in the WP3 Dynamic modelling and production history matching due to high complexity of the reservoir volume and spatial permeability distribution. The history matching was finally achieved in December 2023. The connected milestone M3.2 (transfer of the simulation model to WP8) had to be postponed to early 2024. Submission of a peer-reviewed scientific paper (main result V12) was postponed to early 2024.

The earlier delay in WP4 due to paternity leave of the WP4 leader at NORCE in 2022 have been successfully compensated and two papers were submitted for publications in international highly impacted journals in October 2023.

None of the above-mentioned issues represent a critical obstacle that would jeopardize the achievement of the overall project objectives.

8 SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT FOR THE PURPOSE OF PUBLICATION BY THE PROGRAMME OPERATOR

The Czech-Norwegian project CO₂-SPICER is focussed on preparation of the first pilot geological storage site in the Czech Republic. It has successfully finished the third year of works. The main achievement of this project phase is the finalisation of the 3D static geological and dynamic models of the storage complex. Most of the assessment of geomechanical and geochemical properties of rocks building the reservoir and its overburden have been accomplished. Comprehensive risk analysis was made using all required regional input data. Efficiency of monitoring methods was evaluated for long term supervision of the stored CO₂. Seismological data were collected and preparation of site monitoring plan commenced. Scenarios of further storage site development have been compiled.

Czech version

Česko-norský projekt CO₂-SPICER, zaměřený na přípravu prvního pilotního geologického úložiště CO₂ v ČR, úspěšně uzavřel třetí rok řešení. Nejdůležitějším výsledkem této fáze projektu je aktualizace trojrozměrného statického geologického modelu a vytvoření dynamického modelu úložního komplexu. Bylo provedeno zhodnocení geomechanických a geochemických vlastností hornin tvořících úložiště a jeho nadložní těsnění. Komplexní analýza rizik využila všechna vyžadovaná regionální vstupní data. Proběhlo testování účinnosti monitorovacích metod pro dlouhodobé sledování uloženého CO₂ včetně seismologie. Byly započaty práce na monitorovacím plánu úložního komplexu. Byl sestaven scénář dalšího vývoje úložního komplexu.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The works in the third project period of CO₂-SPICER followed the plan, only minor deviations occurred. All but one main results planned for the period were delivered:

- 3D static geological model of the storage complex was updated and dynamic model of reservoir behaviour was built in WP3. The publication of the results was postponed to early 2024.
- Geomechanical and geochemical properties of reservoir rocks and caprocks (WP4 and WP5) have been practically completed data provided for WP6.
- Risk assessment of the CO₂ storage has been put together in the final report on WP6.
- Third year of field campaigns of baseline monitoring was completed in WP7 including the atmogeochemistry, seismology, ground water measurements and modelling. Preparation of the site monitoring plan commenced.
- Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring was carried out within WP7.
- Scenarios of further storage site development have been compiled in WP8.
- The project outreach was performed through CGS CO₂-SPICER Newsletter, radio interview and VSB-TUO Akademik University Newsletter.
- Czech-Norwegian cooperation in the area of CCS was intensified by active joint research Czech and Norwegian partners, presentation at conferences, meetings, as well as through liaison with other Czech-Norwegian projects funded from EEA/Norway Grants.

In summary, the results of the 3rd project period form a solid base for successful completion of the project goals in the final phase in 2024.

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
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More information about the project can be found at
[CO₂-spicer.geology.cz](https://co2-spicer.geology.cz).

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

T A
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